

Climate_CRICES

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

D. 2.1.1 Report on local capacity building activities to raise knowledge and engage local authorities

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Delivery Date: 28.02.2026

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DOCUMENT SHEET

Project Acronym	Climate_CRICES
Full title	Increasing Climate Change Resilience in Central Europe
Grant Agreement number	CE0200728
Coordinator	Veneto Region
Website	https://www.regione.veneto.it/direzione-ict-e-agenda-digitale

Deliverable number	D.2.1.1
Deliverable name	Report on local capacity building activities to raise knowledge and engage local authorities
Lead Beneficiary	UPWr
WP	WP2
Activity title	A2.1 pilot action preparatory activities
Type	REPORT
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Delivery date	28/02/2026
Main Author	PP8-UPWr and All Partners

Summary

Deliverable D2.1.1 summarises the local capacity-building activities implemented under Activity 2.1 of Climate_CRICES. In line with the Application Form, the eight trainings aimed to involve regional and local authorities (and other relevant stakeholder groups), raise knowledge on the Climate_CRICES strategy and the data-driven dashboard, and define a working pilot roadmap for the following piloting phase, including expectations towards the tool and possible integration pathways for addenda.

Across regions, participants confirmed the relevance of the three core thematic areas addressed by the project (heat and drought, flooding, biodiversity impacts), while repeatedly emphasising that the practical uptake of climate information depends on usability, interpretability, and operational integration into existing planning workflows. Users valued the dashboard as a decision support and communication tool, emphasizing the need for clearer entry points, simplified indicator sets for non-technical users, and improved export and comparison functionalities.

A cross-cutting lesson from the training is that capacity building must be treated as a process rather than a one-off event. Several regions reported uneven baseline competences among participants, especially regarding scenario logic, uncertainty handling and translation of indicators into practical decisions. Short, structured onboarding markedly improved the quality of feedback and stakeholder readiness to test the tool.

The deliverable also consolidates region-specific outputs that inform the pilot phase: priority risks for analysis, reference adaptation documents, expectations towards digital tools, and initial concepts for addendum integration.

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Report on local capacity building activities to raise knowledge and engage local authorities

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Activity 2.1 focused on strengthening the knowledge base and practical readiness of stakeholders to use climate information, indicators and projections in adaptation planning. Local training activities were designed to familiarise stakeholders with the project's approach and the Climate_CRICES dashboard, to elicit needs and barriers, and to translate these into an operational roadmap for pilot actions. This report consolidates partner inputs from local activities and documents the emerging expectations and constraints that must be addressed in the piloting phase

1.2. Scope

This report describes how the eight local trainings were organised, what was delivered, and what inputs were collected to support pilot roadmaps, expectations for the addenda, and tool requirements. The eight local trainings build on earlier project work: stakeholder engagement and a harmonised workshop format, with standard agendas and consistent reporting outputs.

This deliverable covers:

- the design principles and delivery format of the eight local trainings,

- the main training content (strategy logic, dashboard orientation, data-to-decision workflow),

- synthesis of stakeholder expectations and constraints regarding digital tools and data use,

- consolidated inputs for pilot roadmaps and potential addendum integration (as relevant for the next piloting steps).

2. Methodology

2.1. Training design

Local capacity building under Activity 2.1 followed a shared minimum framework agreed within the partnership. The framework defines core modules that ensure comparability across pilot areas (baseline terminology, introduction to the Climate_CRICES logic of

impacts and indicators, and a guided dashboard walkthrough), while allowing partners to adapt content to their regional context and stakeholder needs.

The report is based on partner workshop reports and partner training summaries developed after each local capacity-building activity. Inputs were harmonised using a common structure covering: workshop context and objectives, agenda and format, prioritised climate risks, identified barriers and needs, opportunities for cooperation, implications for pilot action design, and initial concepts for addendum integration.

To ensure comparability across regions, the synthesis distinguishes between cross-cutting findings relevant for the overall dashboard and pilot design, and region-specific findings linked to local planning contexts and reference documents. Where workshops used additional tools (polls, questionnaires, mentoring feedback), results are reported as part of the region summaries where available.

2.2. Dashboard maturity during the trainings

At the beginning of Period 3, the Climate_CRICES dashboard was available as a Prototype V1 with an earlier page structure. During the training cycle, the dashboard structure was revised based on consortium and stakeholder feedback. In the second part of the training period, partners demonstrated a Prototype of Version 2, which was published on 12.01.2026.

In the prototypes used for training, full datasets and automated analyses were not yet available. The trainings therefore focused on introducing the dashboard logic and planned user workflows, presenting the indicator and metadata structure that will govern the next release, and collecting structured feedback on usability, entry points, and minimum functionalities required for pilot testing. Partner inputs (datasets, indicator definitions, and document references) were presented as curated content to be integrated into the next dashboard iterations, enabling early validation before publication of the full feature set.

2.3. Data collection methods

The primary target group are public authorities responsible for climate adaptation planning and implementation, as they are considered the main intended users of the dashboard outputs. In line with the stakeholder mapping approach developed in earlier project phases, partners also involved or invited complementary stakeholder categories (eg NGOs, research and education bodies, and private sector or advisory actors) when relevant for the local planning context.

Feedback and inputs were captured through workshop minutes and moderated discussions, and where applicable through short surveys (baseline expectations and post-event feedback). Collected inputs were structured to support:

- A. dashboard refinement (usability and content requirements),
- B. identification of priority climate impacts and indicators for local use cases, and
- C. definition of working pilot roadmap elements and potential addendum integration options.

3. Overview of the 8 local training activities

In this deliverable, a “local training activity” means a partner-led capacity-building session organised within the partner’s pilot context, primarily targeting regional or local authorities and closely related stakeholder groups. A training activity includes a structured agenda (or a defined module sequence), presentation of Climate_CRICES outputs (strategy and/or dashboard prototypes), and an interactive component to capture user needs and feedback for the pilot phase.

The “8 local training activities” reported in Table 1 refer to one core training session per partner pilot region (LP01+PP02, PP03, PP04, PP05, PP06, PP07, PP08, PP09) implemented in Period 3 and documented through partner workshop reports

Training activities and additional interactions such as conference-style exchanges, networking events, bilateral scoping calls, or external knowledge-exchange meetings are reported in Annex 1 as capacity building. Where multiple sessions occurred, the table reports the main session with the strongest training and feedback function.

Table 1. Training activities overview

PP	Format	Target group	Main focus	Main outputs relevant for pilots
LP01+ PP02	Online + questionnai re-based feedback	Veneto Region and ARPAV technicians, reclamation consortia, water utilities	Baseline knowledge check; key water-climate impacts and data needs. Dashboard briefly shown; preference for operational platforms (ClINE)..	Questionnaire results indicate drought and floods as priority concerns. Participants highlighted the need for accessible, well-documented data and clearer pathways to use climate information in decision-making. A practical addendum-relevant need was emphasised: hydro-meteorological data and analyses for trans-regional river basins (e.g., Adige, Brenta, Livenza, Lemene, Tagliamento), linking planning-oriented summaries with operational water-management perspective.

PP03	In-person + remote access	Regional env/agri stakeholders + researchers	Climate basics, dashboard logic, hands-on testing	Sector-specific indicator needs (agriculture, soil, forestry), need for interpretation guidance, priorities: heat stress and drought (and floods)
PP04	In-person	Regional institutions, parks, tourism, public bodies	Project update, dashboard preview, structured feedback	Need for a clear municipality-level entry point and a two-level dashboard structure (basic and advanced), reduced/prioritised core indicators, municipal comparison and search functionality; biodiversity data gaps and need for expert interpretation; technical stability and browser-independent performance.
PP05	Online	Consultants supporting municipalities	Dashboard logic, scenarios, discussion of gaps	Need for scenario guidance, narrative outputs, "similar municipalities" concept, sustainability concerns, priority: drought and water shortage
PP06	In-person	City office for strategic planning (GEOS)	Dashboard walkthrough + feedback for SECAP addendum	Priorities: heat/UHI and flash floods; need for intuitive navigation, export/import options, stronger indicator-measure links
PP07	Online	Municipal, regional, federal actors	Practical use of dashboard for adaptation planning	Barriers: funding constraints, limited staff capacity, lack of legal enforceability, political inertia and awareness gaps; dashboard valued for justification and communication; need for early-stage ("phase zero") planning support, curated practice-oriented packages, and concise evidence-based case briefs (incl. cost-benefit narratives); stronger cooperation via standards, contact overviews and Euroregion-level coordination. Also requested: systematic translations of key materials, better visibility of existing initiatives/tools, and establishing a community of users to support peer learning and uptake.
PP08	Online workshop	Local and regional authorities + research/advisory + private sector + NGOs	Dashboard demonstration, DPW context, structured feedback on data and usability	Priority risks: flooding/heavy rainfall, drought/water scarcity, heat; strong demand for an interpretation layer, spatial layers and reporting exports; strongest data gaps for monitoring effects (impact tracking), risk identification, investment justification, action planning and reporting; practical format expectations (incl. SHP);

				usability barriers: interface readability and language accessibility (need for clearer explanations and translations)
PP09	Online	Regional institutions, municipalities, ARR	Dashboard demo + practical adaptation webinars	Priorities: flooding/heavy rain, heat, drought, biodiversity; needs: exports, metadata, data library, responsibilities for updates

4. Training content delivered

Local trainings were designed around a shared minimum module set to ensure comparability across pilot areas, while allowing partners to adapt examples and discussion topics to local needs. The common framework included a baseline module on used terminology, scenarios relevant for planning, an introduction to the Climate_CRICES logic (impacts, indicators, data sources and metadata), and a hands-on module demonstrating the dashboard and guiding stakeholders through example use cases.

Across trainings, the interactive part was used to capture: stakeholder needs and expectations towards the tool, barriers to data use (including interpretation of uncertainty), and initial inputs for working pilot roadmaps and possible addendum integration options.

5. Outcomes and feedback

5.1. Stakeholders capacity and attitude

Several partners report uneven baseline competence among stakeholders, both between and within regions. While technical users (eg water managers, consultants, researchers) can usually interpret indicators, scenario logic and basic uncertainty concepts, many municipal and policy users require structured onboarding and guided examples to translate climate information into planning-relevant conclusions. This was particularly visible in the Hungarian context, where participants highlighted difficulties in interpreting multi-scenario outputs and uncertainty, and asked for clearer guidance on how to use projections in municipal planning practice.

At the same time, workshops confirmed a generally constructive attitude towards the project and strong interest in practical, ready-to-use outputs - but also a clear expectation that the tool and related materials must be adapted to real-world capacity constraints. In Saxony, stakeholders pointed to limited municipal resources (staff and funding) and to

governance barriers, including weak enforceability of adaptation measures. This implies that high awareness is insufficient; implementation capacity remains a bottleneck unless the project provides simple workflows, practical templates, and 'phase zero' support (entry-level guidance

Across cases, capacity gaps were not limited to technical understanding of climate information. Partners also reported uncertainty regarding institutional roles and responsibilities, especially where planning competences and data ownership are split across multiple levels of administration or across sectoral institutions. In the Polish context, this included unclear institutional competences and differences in baseline knowledge among stakeholder groups, which affects both the pace and the depth of engagement during capacity-building activities.

Overall, the trainings suggest that effective capacity building requires a tiered approach: basic onboarding for municipal and policy audiences (definitions, scenarios, uncertainty, and "how to use outputs"), complemented by more advanced modules for technical users focusing on methodological details, dataset provenance and reproducible workflows. This layered structure is also important for stakeholder attitude: it reduces frustration among non-experts while allowing technically advanced users to test and validate assumptions, which in turn strengthens trust in dashboard outputs and in the addendum integration pathway.

Inputs from PP07 also show that "capacity" constraints are not only about knowledge. Stakeholders repeatedly pointed to structural limits that block uptake of climate information even when awareness exists: staffing shortages, constrained municipal budgets, lack of legally binding adaptation requirements, and political inertia. This implies that capacity building should include early-stage scoping support and "ready-to-use" justification materials, not only indicator literacy.

5.2 Expectations

A recurrent request is to reduce complexity for first-time users while retaining analytical depth for advanced users. In Burgenland, stakeholders explicitly proposed a two-level model: a simple layer with 2-3 core indicators and a deeper layer for expert use, combined with clearer tables and a municipality-first entry point.

Other regions stressed the need for export and reporting functions, scenario and time-horizon comparisons, and clearer interpretation guidance (especially for multi-scenario projections).

Across trainings, stakeholders expressed interest in a tool that supports real planning tasks and not only data exploration. Recurring expectations include:

- **Usability and clarity:** simplified navigation, clearer structure, and reduced complexity for non-expert users: the dashboard, in its current form, is not yet sufficiently user-friendly - the amount of content and the level of complexity can quickly become overwhelming - Eisenstadt, 19.11.2025).
- **Interpretation support:** short guidance on how to read indicators, interpret scenarios, and avoid misinterpretation of uncertainty (“it is confusing for municipal staff that databases containing climate parameters generally include several different future scenarios for the same phenomenon. The concept of uncertainty is difficult to understand for the primary target group, making them uncertain about the usability of the data” - CDDA).
- **Curated selection:** stakeholders repeatedly indicated they do not have time to verify long lists of guidelines and datasets. They expect the dashboard to offer a curated selection of the most useful materials (with transparent metadata and short practical support), supported by filters that quickly surface content matching their concrete needs.
- **Planning-oriented outputs:** maps and concise visual summaries that can be reused in documents, briefings, and decision processes.
- **Comparability:** ability to compare areas, scenarios, or periods in a consistent way (especially relevant in cross-border contexts).
- Cross-border users additionally stressed **“non-technical” enablers of uptake:** translations of key guidance, improved visibility of already existing tools and good practices, and a lightweight user community for exchange and feedback.

PP04 explicitly requested a two-level dashboard structure (basic and advanced), a reduced set of core indicators for non-technical users, and functions supporting municipal comparison and search. PP08 emphasised that availability of data is not enough without interpretability: users need simple definitions, sources clearly attached to indicators, and practical exports for reporting (with SHP still being a “real-life” expectation despite its limitations). PP07 highlighted the need for early-stage (“phase zero”) guidance that helps municipalities scope options and justify action, supported by concise evidence-based case briefs.

Stakeholders repeatedly requested indicator sets that are actionable for local planning and that connect climate drivers to impacts and measures. Needs expressed in the documented trainings include:

- focus on heat, drought, water scarcity, heavy precipitation and flood-related impacts as frequent planning priorities.
- clearer treatment of uncertainty and multi-scenario outputs, including plain-language explanations and recommended use in decision-making.
- improved coverage of thematic areas that often lack easy datasets at local scale (for example biodiversity-related content - “Mangel an Biodiversitätsdaten und Experteneinschätzung” - Eisenstadt, 19.11.2025; “biodiversity aspects are still insufficiently reflected in adaptation planning.” - UJEP, online).
- The above needs align with the common minimum framework, where dashboard exploration is paired with structured collection of indicator requirements and gaps.

A recurring theme is that barriers are not only technical, but also organisational and interpretative. Documented constraints include:

- limited capacity in administrations to interpret climate projections and scenario uncertainty without guidance, resulting in low confidence in using outputs in official planning.
- time and staffing constraints, with planning tasks frequently supported by external experts (consulting firms), which creates a need for clear handover-ready outputs and common interpretation rules.
- early-stage tool complexity and the need to prioritise a minimal set of functions that support real workflows.

In cross-border context, stakeholders highlighted the need for comparable indicators, aligned interpretation guidance, and clarity on how regional differences in governance and datasets affect joint planning. These needs are consistent with the tri-border training and addendum framing reported in the tri-border documentation.

6. Pilot action input

6.1 Priority risks and thematic focus

Across local trainings, the three thematic areas selected for the pilot phase (heat and drought, flooding, biodiversity impacts) were consistently considered relevant. At the same time, partners reported clear territorial differences in the perceived urgency and framing of these risks, reflecting both local exposure and the planning contexts in which stakeholders operate. In practice, the workshops show that stakeholders do not treat these themes as isolated categories: heat and drought were often discussed together with water scarcity and ecosystem stress, while flooding was frequently linked to heavy rainfall extremes, pluvial flooding and short-response catchments.

- LP01+PP02 (Veneto): priority climate impacts identified with stakeholders were related to drought (water scarcity), questionnaire results mentioned also flooding.
- PP04 (Burgenland) confirmed heat stress and drought as dominant priorities, with local heavy rainfall also highlighted.
- In the Central Danube Priority Area (PP05), drought and water scarcity emerged as the dominant concern. Participants emphasised that local administrations often struggle to interpret multi-scenario climate outputs and to justify adaptation measures in the absence of clear guidance. This strengthens the case for pilot analyses that combine drought-related indicators with short interpretative narratives and decision-relevant “how to use” notes, rather than presenting scenario outputs alone.
- In Zagreb (PP06), stakeholders prioritised heat-related impacts (including urban heat island effects) and flash floods, which are particularly relevant for urban planning and civil protection contexts. The workshop discussions linked these priorities to the practical need for clear dashboard workflows and exports that can directly support SECAP updates and communication with decision-makers.
- PP07 (Saxony) framed the thematic priorities through implementation constraints, stressing that risks become actionable only when linked to enforceable governance, funding and staffing realities
- PP08 (Lower Silesia): stakeholders prioritised flooding/heavy rainfall, drought/water scarcity and heat, with strong emphasis on urban heat stress (incl. UHI framing) and retention-related solutions, highlighted the need to strengthen biodiversity and ecosystem evidence in planning.
- In the Liberec Region (PP09), flooding and heavy rainfall were highlighted as a key thematic focus, while heat, drought and biodiversity impacts remained important co-themes. The workshop also pointed to the need for a curated data library,

metadata and simple algorithms usable by municipalities, which suggests that the pilot should not only test indicators, but also demonstrate concrete workflows for integrating outputs into local planning documents and assessments.

- The tri-border workshop reinforced heat and drought as a top priority in voting results, but also brought a stronger cross-border perspective on feasibility constraints. Discussions emphasised differences in data availability and granularity between countries and the specific challenge of small catchments where harmonised datasets may be sparse or inconsistent. This indicates that, for the tri-border pilot context, thematic focus must be accompanied by explicit documentation of assumptions, harmonisation choices and limitations, especially when comparing indicators across borders.

Finally, biodiversity impacts were repeatedly recognised as relevant across regions but also as the thematic area most constrained by data gaps and methodological challenges. Stakeholders in Burgenland explicitly stressed the need for biodiversity expertise and better data availability, and tri-border discussions similarly pointed to fragmented sources and lack of harmonised indicators. This implies that biodiversity-related pilot work may need to focus first on feasibility and interpretability (what can be credibly shown, at which scale, and with what uncertainty), rather than on broad indicator coverage.

6.2. Data gaps and needs for interpretation

Local trainings consistently confirmed that data availability alone is not the main barrier. Stakeholders repeatedly returned to two linked issues: (i) gaps in specific thematic domains (most notably biodiversity), and (ii) the need for an interpretation layer that explains what indicators mean, what assumptions sit behind them, and how results should be used in planning practice.

- **Biodiversity as the most constrained thematic domain**

Biodiversity data gaps were highlighted across regions, both in terms of missing datasets and in terms of methodological ambiguity (what should be measured, at what spatial scale, and how to interpret trends under uncertainty). In Burgenland, participants explicitly pointed to missing biodiversity data and stressed the need for stronger expert involvement to ensure credibility and usability of biodiversity-related outputs.

Tri-border discussions reinforced this concern, emphasising the lack of harmonised biodiversity indicators across countries and the fragmentation of relevant sources. This creates a practical challenge for pilot work: even when datasets exist, cross-border comparability can be limited by differences in classification systems, monitoring methods, spatial resolution, and update cycles.

- **Interpretation needs: from values to decisions**

Across contexts, stakeholders signalled that they need more than maps and charts. They require interpretation support that clarifies scenario logic, uncertainty, and “so what” implications for planning decisions. This is particularly relevant where municipal staff or non-technical policy actors are expected to use outputs directly, or where planning work is outsourced and public administrations need to remain competent clients. The Hungarian workshop illustrates this clearly: participants reported difficulties in interpreting multi-scenario results and uncertainty, which affects their ability to justify adaptation actions in municipal workflows.

- **Preference for curated resources over more raw data**

In several contexts, stakeholders asked for a curated “data library” rather than additional raw datasets. The core expectation was not “more layers”, but better support for finding, understanding and reusing existing information. In the Czech workshop, this was framed as a practical need for a structured data library with metadata and simple algorithms or calculators that municipalities can apply without building their own analytical pipelines.

This preference aligns with the broader usability feedback: stakeholders are more likely to adopt the tool and addenda if they can quickly locate a small number of trusted indicators, understand their provenance, and export consistent outputs for planning documents.

- **Implications for the pilot phase and addendum development**

These findings imply that pilot work should explicitly include: (i) transparency on dataset provenance and limitations (metadata, update frequency, spatial resolution), (ii) concise interpretation notes tailored to stakeholder roles, and (iii) a pragmatic approach to biodiversity outputs that prioritises feasibility and credibility over broad coverage. Where harmonisation is not possible, documenting limitations and assumptions becomes part of the deliverable rather than a weakness to hide.

7. Addendum input

Across local trainings, partners and stakeholders implicitly converged on a similar set of requirements for addendum usability and uptake:

- **Modularity and fit to planning cycles**

Addenda are most feasible when structured as modular components that can be plugged into existing planning documents and workflows (rather than a single long

report). This is particularly relevant in contexts where planning responsibilities are distributed across institutions and document updates follow strict cycles.

- **Interpretation layer, not only indicators**

Stakeholders repeatedly stressed the need for guidance on interpretation (uncertainty, scenario logic, translating values into decisions). This implies that addenda should include short interpretation notes, assumptions, and “how to use” instructions, not only figures and maps.

- **Export and reporting as enabling condition**

In several regions, the feasibility of integrating dashboard outputs into addenda depends on practical reporting features (exports, consistent visuals, references to datasets and metadata). This is why addendum integration is tightly coupled with dashboard development. Uptake pathway needs an “owner”

- **Uptake pathway needs an “owner”**

Addenda are easier to integrate when there is a clear institutional owner (authority, programme manager, strategic planning unit) who can promote uptake into formal documents or operational programmes. Where the formal AP is not the same entity as the data owner (eg river basin institutions), integration must target the organisations that actually use those documents in regional practice. ment priorities.

- **Cross-border coherence in shared basins**

In the tri-border context, addendum integration is constrained by differences in data granularity, calculation methods and legislation. Therefore, addenda should explicitly document harmonisation choices and limitations, rather than aiming for artificial uniformity.

8. Conclusions

Local capacity-building activities under Activity 2.1 confirm that the Climate_CRICES approach is perceived as relevant and timely across pilot regions. Stakeholders consistently recognised the value of a shared framework combining climate projections, indicator-based analysis and a dashboard supporting evidence-based adaptation planning. At the same time, the trainings show that effective uptake depends less on the sheer volume of data and more on usability, interpretability and practical integration into existing planning workflows.

A cross-cutting conclusion is that stakeholder capacity and attitudes are strongly shaped by operational constraints. Technical users can engage with scenario logic and indicators, but municipal and policy users often need structured onboarding, concrete examples and interpretation guidance to translate dashboard outputs into decisions. The workshops also highlighted governance and resource barriers, including limited staff and funding and unclear institutional competences, which means that even well-designed tools require clear entry points and lightweight workflows that match real municipal capacity.

Regarding thematic focus, the three pilot themes (heat and drought, flooding, biodiversity impacts) were consistently considered relevant, but their ranking differs across territories. This confirms the need for a flexible pilot design that can accommodate local priority profiles while maintaining a harmonised core set of analyses. Biodiversity impacts were repeatedly recognised as important but also identified as the most constrained domain due to data gaps, fragmented sources and limited harmonisation potential across borders, strengthening the case for an expert-supported and transparent feasibility-first approach in the pilot phase.

Finally, local trainings confirmed that addenda are a feasible and practical format for connecting dashboard outputs with formal planning processes. Addenda can provide a concrete entry point for authorities, but their integration requires modular structure, clear ownership and a transparent interpretation layer (assumptions, limitations, scenario logic). The strong stakeholder preference for curated resources (a data library with metadata and simple calculators) suggests that the project should prioritise reproducible workflows and decision-ready outputs over expanding raw data coverage.

Annex 1: Summary of the capacity building by partners

Annexes 2-10: Partners' Workshop reports

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

D. 2.1.1 Report on local capacity building activities to raise knowledge and engage local authorities

ANNEX 1: Summary of the capacity building by partners

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Delivery Date: 28.02.2026

Summary of the training

LP1+PP02

- **Activities performed**

Workshop

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

The workshop allowed us to assess stakeholders' initial level of knowledge and attitudes regarding climate change, available tools, and regional adaptation policies.

Participants demonstrated a good awareness of regional climate impacts, particularly drought and water scarcity, consistent with their professional profiles, which are primarily related to water resource management and land reclamation consortia. However, they noted a lack of complete understanding of the extent of the climate changes underway and limited immediate availability of consolidated data and indicators. Participants expressed a need for a better data accessibility.

Regarding climate tools and data, some participants were already familiar with some of the platforms and products presented, while for many, the meeting represented a first opportunity for discovery, generating interest and requests for further information.

Regarding adaptation strategies, it emerged that, although the adoption of formal plans by every institution is not mandatory, several entities, particularly land reclamation consortia, have already adopted operational tools to address climate impacts, often anticipating the development of structured strategies in response to concrete and immediate needs.

The attitudes that emerged indicate a high level of interest in using weather and climate data in daily work and a positive perception of the usefulness of digital tools in supporting decision-making. The need for greater data integration between regions was also highlighted, given the supraregional nature of river basins, given the current fragmentation of information management and sharing systems.

The most significant interactions involved technical profiles, particularly water resource managers. Finally, initial findings from the questionnaire confirm a strong demand for institutional action, even through complex or potentially unpopular measures, to effectively address the impacts of climate change.

The project's objectives were further clarified, especially thanks to the feedback from the questionnaires.

The dashboard was presented only briefly and was not considered central by participants; greater interest was shown in data platforms such as CliNE and the available operational information. The technicians present, particularly those involved in water resources management, demonstrated excellent skills in interpreting climate indicators, maps, time series, and future scenarios.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

- **specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

Based on the interactions with participants, the climate impacts considered to be priority were drought and floods, also chosen given the type of stakeholders present. (From questionnaire results.)

- **Specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.**

The Veneto Regional Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change and the related annex containing the Adaptation Measures.

- **Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

Interest in accessing weather-climate data also thanks to the support guided by specific platforms. The participants were mainly technical.

- **Plan for addendum integration**

Discussions revealed the interest of some entities (Land Reclamation Consortia) in accessing hydro-meteorological data for river basins crossing two regions. This entirely logical request conflicts with regional land management, monitoring systems, and databases approach. The issue is particularly relevant for land reclamation consortia operating in the Adige, Brenta, Livenza, Lemene, and Tagliamento river basins.

Data analysis for a trans-regional area has a climatological aspect (monthly rainfall distribution, differences from the average, etc.) for planning purposes, and an operational aspect aimed at assessing the current situation in real time.

This issue was not considered in the Climate_CRICES project. It is not easy to solve, given the organization of regional entities. However, we could propose

interventions to address the problem or at least take it into account in future regional planning.

- Identification of data application areas

The questionnaire for the stakeholders who attended the meeting on January 27, 2026, contained the question: "Which climate phenomena do you believe pose the greatest threat to your sector or area over the next 5-10 years?" The following responses were collected:

17 out of 50 responses highlighted the importance of water scarcity and prolonged drought;

16 responses highlighted the importance of floods and hydrogeological instability;

9 responses highlighted the importance of extreme events;

4 responses concerned heat waves;

4 responses emphasized the importance of sea level rise.

The importance of floods and extreme weather events is undeniable, and regional authorities are already actively working in these areas, especially after the flood of November 2010.

However, especially for stakeholders such as Land Reclamation Consortia (agricultural irrigation water) and Drinking Water Management Agencies, drought represents a significant impact that must be addressed in planning and in operational management.

PP03

- **Activities performed**

The training workshop for the Piedmont pilot held on 19th November 2025, was structured along 3 main modules:

- Module 1 on Climate change fundamentals presenting global and regional climate trends, concepts such as risk, vulnerability, scenarios (GCM-RCM-local), differences between mitigation and adaptation, and sector-specific impacts with a focus on agriculture.

- Module 2 on the Climate_CRICES data logic: Introduction to data sources (Copernicus, national meteorological services, ARPA datasets), indicator rationale, and existing limitations.
- Module 3 as a practical session on the Climate_CRICES dashboard, a hands-on exploration of heat, drought, flood, biodiversity, and agriculture-related indicators; identification of locally relevant metrics with mini-plenary feedback.

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

The participants were all quite well versed on the general concepts and were quite interested in the potential contribution of the dashboard. Progress in building knowledge of the project strategy and the data dashboard, assessment of the readiness of officials to use the dashboard and their competencies in forecasting climate change impacts.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

- **specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

The Piedmont regional pilots will focus on two specific climate change impacts to be analysed, that is heat and drought and floods

- **Specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.**

Regional Strategy on Climate Change of 2022.

- **Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

The main expectations that emerged from the training session were mostly related to agriculture, as officials from the Agriculture Department were quite actively involved in the activity:

Technical elements: enhancement of heat-stress and drought indicators relevant for agriculture, possibly inclusion of forestry-related metrics as well as improved soil data (organic matter, water retention, biological activity); clearer documentation and interpretation guidelines.

Organisational elements: clearer workflows for integrating dashboard outputs into planning.

Practical elements: user support during early adoption, examples of dashboard-informed decisions and iterative refinement based on real operational needs.

- Identification of data application areas

Currently open data are lacking on this topic in the Piedmont territory, although they may be quite useful both for Climate_CRICES and other projects as well. The Agriculture Sector of Piedmont Region was involved in the training activities, as dashboard data would be useful for them

PP04

- **Activities performed**

Forschung Burgenland (PP04) implemented in-person capacity building workshop in Eisenstadt (Burgenland) to initiate structured stakeholder dialogue on climate impacts, data needs and cooperation formats to present and test the updated Climate_CRICES dashboard with end users and collect structured usability feedback.

The workshop (19 November 2025) provided a live dashboard demonstration and a structured feedback session focused on indicator prioritisation, municipal entry points and target-group-oriented usability. Participants included representatives from Office of the Burgenland Provincial Government (Department 4), Nationalpark Neusiedler See, ARGE Naturparke, KLAR Leithaland, KLAR ökoEnergieLand, KLAR Rosalia-Kogelberg, Burgenland Tourism, Research Burgenland GmbH and Nursing Service Burgenland.

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

Across the session, stakeholders showed high awareness of climate impacts in Burgenland and strong interest in using data-driven tools for practical adaptation planning at municipal and regional levels. At the same time, baseline capacity to interpret complex indicator systems and “interconnections” between indicators was uneven, and participants explicitly requested clearer structure, prioritised core indicators, and guidance/training materials to support consistent interpretation. The attitude towards the dashboard was constructive and solution-oriented: stakeholders welcomed the tool’s potential for decision support and communication, but stressed that uptake depends on stable performance, browser-independent usability, and a clear, municipality-oriented entry point.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

- **Specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

Stakeholders consistently prioritised (1) heat and drought (including heat stress and water availability), (2) flood risk / heavy precipitation and local extreme rainfall events, and (3) biodiversity-related impacts, with an emphasis on addressing current gaps in biodiversity data and expert input.

- **Specific climate adaptation plan serving as a reference document**

Participants linked expected dashboard use primarily to municipal and regional adaptation planning and coordination formats already active in Burgenland (including KLAR!-related planning/reporting contexts), and stressed the need to align outputs with real administrative and planning workflows rather than producing additional standalone strategies.

- **Participants' expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

Key needs clustered around the following main aspects. First, stakeholders expressed the need for a reduced and prioritised set of core indicators to make the information easier to interpret and use. Second, a two-level dashboard structure was considered important, distinguishing between a basic level for political decision-makers and a more advanced level for technical staff, thereby addressing the needs of different user groups. Third, functionalities that allow municipal comparison and easy search were highlighted as particularly useful. Fourth, stakeholders emphasised the importance of clear visualisations combined with concise explanatory narratives to support decision-making. Finally, onboarding support in the form of short guidance materials and follow-up training sessions was identified as necessary to facilitate effective use of the dashboard.

Point-to-point enumeration:

1. Reduced, prioritised set of core indicators
2. Two-level dashboard logic (basic vs. advanced) to serve different user groups (political decision-makers vs. technical staff)
3. Municipal comparison and search functionality
4. Clear visualisations and concise narratives for decision-makers
5. Onboarding support via short guidance and follow-up trainings

- **Plan for addendum integration**

FB inputs indicate that addendum components should be designed as practical, evidence-oriented modules that can be referenced in existing municipal/regional planning and reporting formats (rather than replacing them).

Stakeholders highlighted that such modules would be most useful when they: translate prioritised indicators into planning-relevant conclusions, support justification of measures for decision-makers, and include interpretation guidance (especially for biodiversity-related content where data and expertise gaps remain).

- **Identification of data application areas**

For stakeholders in Burgenland, the main added value of climate data and dashboard outputs lies in improving the understanding and prioritisation of climate risks at the municipal level, including heat, drought, heavy rainfall, flood risk, and biodiversity stress. The data also support the evidence-based justification and communication of adaptation measures and help raise awareness among different target groups. Another important benefit is the improved cross-sector coordination between public administration, KLAR! actors, protected area and nature park stakeholders, and in some cases the tourism sector. In addition, dashboard outputs can be integrated into routine planning and reporting processes, particularly when exportable data and clear visualisations are available.

PP05

- **Activities performed**

The CDDA organized a workshop for future users of the dashboard on December 12, 2025. The target group of the workshop was professionals who, as employees of consulting firms, assist municipalities in their climate change-related planning activities. There were two reasons for selecting this specific target group. On the one hand, we did not consider it appropriate to show the dashboard in its current state to its primary target group, i.e., municipal government employees. Secondly, employees in the consulting sector in the Middle Danube Region have the most background information for further developing the dashboard and expanding its professional input.

The workshop consisted of a short introductory presentation on local climate challenges, followed by a detailed presentation of the dashboard, including data models and various climate scenarios used in the project. The second part of the workshop was an interactive discussion, during which all participants had the opportunity to express their opinions on the given topic and make suggestions for further development of the dashboard and, more generally, for enhancing the professional support provided by Climate_CRICES.

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

The workshop participants noted that local government employees are generally unaware of the digital data currently available on the local impacts of climate change. Even if they have heard of these databases, they are often unable to interpret the logic behind the data and climate models. However, there is consensus that it would be important to take future climate projections into account in local planning. However, it is important to emphasize that urban planning tasks, particularly the preparation of situation assessments and data analyses, are typically carried out in the Middle Danube Region not by officials but by external experts on the basis of business contracts. At the same time, it is important that local government officials understand the logic behind climate forecasts and are familiar with the data sources on climate change impacts. This would enable the analyses prepared by experts to be incorporated more effectively into local government decision-making.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

- **specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

The workshop participants considered drought and water shortage to be the most serious climate change-related challenges in the region. At the same time, they noted that this phenomenon is usually accompanied by heat waves in summer, which further exacerbate the devastating effects of drought due to increased evaporation. However, drought is not limited to summer; last winter, for example, was particularly dry. All of this has a serious impact on the region's wildlife, contributing to a decline in biodiversity. Overall, therefore, the most serious climate risk in the Middle Danube region is drought/water shortage, followed by an increase in the frequency of heat waves and, as a consequence of the former, a decline in biodiversity.

- **Specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.**

The Middle Danube Region is divided into two geographically distinct parts: the hilly region west of the Danube and the flat landscape east of the Danube. The two areas belong to two different counties (NUTS3 regions), both of which have climate strategies (Tolna County Climate Strategy, Bács-Kiskun County Climate Strategy), and both of which include climate adaptation components. Accordingly, these serve as reference documents in the field of climate adaptation in the CentralDanube Region.

- **Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

The workshop participants agreed that guidelines on the application of future climate model outputs are particularly important for local actors. Several databases and professional guidelines are available in Hungary to assist with this, and it would be important to collect them and display them together on a single platform. The dashboard is expected to be suitable for this function.

The workshop participants made some specific suggestions for further developing the dashboard to make it easier for officials to interpret the data it contains (e.g., the dashboard should show that, based on the past decades, pessimistic climate scenarios are closer to current trends in CentralDanube Region; integration of attention-grabbing messages and pop-ups indicating that adaptation measures should be tailored to local conditions; development of user guidelines, etc.).

- **Plan for addendum integration**

The addendum being prepared within the framework of Climate_CRICES plays a very important role in the CentralDanube Region for two reasons. On the one hand, the Operational Program for the CentralDanube Region currently does not address the issue of climate change adaptation in any significant way, even though it has a major impact on the socio-economic processes in the region. Secondly, the project partner (CDDA) is in a position to directly promote the incorporation of the proposals formulated in the addendum into the region's operational program.

The development of the addendum will be significantly supported by pilot action, as they will help to understand, firstly, what knowledge local actors have about the

local effects of climate change, secondly, what knowledge and data they need for this, and thirdly, what adaptation measures are needed.

In the CentralDanube Region, the pilot action focuses on viticulture. However, we plan to compile the addendum with a broader focus in order to comprehensively integrate the challenges and adaptation measures related to local climate change impacts (heat and Doughts; flood; loss of biodiversity) into the operational program of the Middle Danube Region.

- **Identification of data application areas**

The workshop participants agreed that one of the main roles of climate data is to draw attention to the seriousness of climate change-related problems, as it supports everyday experiences with numerical data. This increases the motivation of local stakeholders to implement adaptation measures.

Another obvious role of climate data is to identify the conditions that need to be taken into account when implementing long-term developments by specifying future climate characteristics, albeit with a degree of uncertainty (e.g., in viticulture, climate data determine which species should be planted in order to ensure long-term yields).

PP06

- **Activities performed**

REGEA organized a workshop during the pilot phase on 27 October 2025. The workshop was attended by the City of Zagreb's Office for Strategic Planning and Development (GEOS) as our key stakeholder. In addition to a general introduction to the Climate_CRICES project, the main focus was placed on explaining the dashboard and its functionalities in order to stimulate interest as much as possible. The ultimate goal was to collect feedback related to the dashboard, particularly regarding areas where stakeholders see potential for further improvement.

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

The stakeholder demonstrated strong interest in using the dashboard. As this is an office responsible for spatial planning, the tool can be of great value to their work. We agreed that with a higher number of training sessions, the use of the dashboard would become more effective and of higher quality, which would further increase

interest. For some users, a lack of knowledge could pose a challenge; however, we agreed that more targeted training could mitigate this issue or at least reduce it to a minimum.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

The next step is to organize a larger number of well-targeted training sessions aimed at increasing stakeholders' knowledge, testing the dashboard, and exploring additional possibilities for its integration into stakeholders' daily work. The number of training sessions will depend on stakeholders' progress, with the high level of interest in the tool representing a facilitating factor.

- **specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

In discussions with stakeholders, we concluded that the priority climate change impacts are heatwaves leading to the formation of urban heat islands, as well as flash floods caused by intense thunderstorms. These impacts pose risks not only to infrastructure but also significantly threaten human health and lives.

In addition to these two impacts, biodiversity was also highlighted as a key priority, as it was agreed that it has so far received insufficient attention in spatial planning.

- **Specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.**

In our case, the main reference document is the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) of the City of Zagreb from 2019. This document is currently in need of revision and update, which is one of the key objectives to be achieved through the implementation of this project. The dashboard is therefore intended to support the renewal of the SECAP by providing data, indicators and analytical insights for evidence-based climate adaptation planning.

In addition, the Climate City Contract (CCC), which is currently under development, was also identified as an important strategic document. One of the project's goals is to contribute to the improvement and strengthening of the CCC by integrating climate data and adaptation-related outputs generated within the Climate_CRICES project.

- **Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

The main suggestion from our stakeholders is that the dashboard should be as user-friendly as possible. They find the overall content extremely interesting, but consider it most important that the desired information (measures, indicators, regional comparisons, etc.) can be accessed as quickly as possible. We also concluded that further training sessions will support faster and more effective use of the dashboard

- **Plan for addendum integration**

In discussions with stakeholders, we identified the possibility of adding addendums to the City of Zagreb’s SECAP in the form of annexes linked to the main document. Given that a revision of the SECAP is planned, we consider this approach feasible.

We also see the potential for direct integration of the addendums into the Climate City Contract. As this document is currently under development, we believe this will be achievable.

In addition, since the project addresses climate change impacts that represent major challenges for the City of Zagreb, we expect there to be strong interest in these updates and improvements.

PP07

1) Activities performed

IÖR followed a three-phased approach

Phase 1 Scoping:

In this initial phase, we intend to understand the current status of climate change (CC) adaptation in Saxony. This is very timely since the Federal State of Saxony has to have passed its state-wide climate change adaptation strategy by the end of January 2027 as per the binding steps stipulated in the German Adaptation Strategy. We are therefore at a very favorable point in the policy cycle. The Ministry in charge (A06 Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit, Energie und Klimaschutz formerly called Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Energie, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Landwirtschaft) has finalized the draft elements of the strategy and is now engaging in extensive consultations (see list that we have engaged in below). The strategy will entail adaptation measures that will need to happen at a state level, but also mandate municipalities to develop their own strategies and implementation measures.

→ **We therefore see a large potential in influencing this process and policy.**

At the same time, the administrative institution in charge of ultimately implementing the strategy, the Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie (LfULG) (A05), is supporting the consultative process and preparing the grounds to support (a) the development of the municipal adaptation strategies and (b) their adaptation measures. For this, the LfULG has put or is putting in place several measures, such as:

- (1) A network of municipal climate change adaptation managers that meets regularly to discuss their implementation challenges.
- (2) A bi-weekly office hour ([Eine Stunde fürs Klima](#)) where different climate change-related topics are briefly presented, and then an open question and answer format allows an exchange of views.
- (3) Extensive climate change impact and adaptation measures information through their [Rekis Kommunal platform](#), which allows obtaining easy overview information, but also in-depth expert information, if needed.
- (4) In the same site, they are working on a capacity development/training program that will be launched towards the end of 2026 to walk municipalities through the process of developing and implementing CC adaptation plans and measures.

Lastly, the Landkreis Görlitz (A03) is very active in its plans towards sustainability and climate change mitigation. A major project is starting on adaptation measures to heavy precipitation events which we have been invited to work and support.

Phase 2 - Conversations with key partners (July to November 2025)

To understand the status, we have taken part in activities, had a number of conversations with key partners and other actors, and presented Climate_CRICES at a range of events. These are listed below.

Date of the interaction	Name of the event/partner	Aim
29.07.2025	Kurt Brüggemann, CC	Get a general understanding of

	adaptation manager of the City of Leipzig (1.5 hour zoom call)	the role of a CC adaptation manager, current challenges, tools that are available
18.08.2025	Leipziger Forum Klimaanpassung http://www.leipzig.de/klimaanpassung	Witness the consultative process of the presentation of the draft CC adaptation strategy of the City of Leipzig to better understand the technical, political and practical challenges of the process → see report (in German)
01.10.2025	Status Colloquium on Air Quality & Climate Change, Pillnitz https://www.luft.sachsen.de/download/luft/2025_Einladung_Statuskolloquium_Luft-Klima.pdf → Invitation by A05 to this event	Information booth on Climate_CRICES showcasing the project and the dashboard; networking with partners and municipalities → see report (in English)
08.10.2025	Consultative conversation with Jan Schönfelder (A03) on their current projects and interactions with Climate_CRICES (1 hour online conversation)	Explore opportunities for the 'training' event and interactions with municipalities, as well as for further communication with A03
28.10.2025	Fachtag Klimaanpassung für sächsische Landkreise und Gemeinden , Dresden → Invitation by A05 to this event	Witness the presentation and consultative process of the draft CC adaptation strategy of the State of Saxony to municipalities. networking with partners and municipalities → see report (in English)
29.10.2025	Consultative conversation with Kristin Kleeberg (A05), in charge of the CC adaptation network and the revamping of the REKIS Kommunal site (45 min online conversation)	Explore opportunities for the 'training' event and interactions with municipalities, as well as for further communication with A05
10 and 12.11.2025	Online-Beteiligungsprozess zur Erarbeitung der Sächsischen Anpassungsstrategie an den Klimawandel	Official consultative process on the current draft CC adaptation strategy of the State of Saxony for research and technical

	→ Invitation by A06 to this event	institutions.
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The participation in these events allowed for a deeper understanding of the current issues, needs, and activities on climate change adaptation policies and implementation in Saxony as a state, but also within the municipalities.

Phase 3 - 'Training' and space for collaboration (October 2025 to February 2026)

Our approach focused on presenting the current findings (WP1 output O1) and outputs of Climate-CRICES, in particular those that will be implemented in the new dashboard version, and to discuss these with different user groups. As such, the following events were attended or (co-) organized.

Date	Duration and modality	Name/type of interaction	Target audience	Aim
21.10.2025	FtF in Markersdorf, in German and in Polish,	Informations- und Erfahrungsaustausch zum Thema „Klimaveränderungsmanagement und Starkregenvorsorge“, Markersdorf → Invitation by A03 to this event → in collaboration with PP08 and PP09	Municipalities and technical staff of the German side of the tri-border region	Presentation on Climate_CRICES showcasing the project and the dashboard; interactive feedback session (see Plickers results here and here); networking with partners and municipalities
20.11.2025	Online, 3.5 hours, in English (see Agenda in the Annex as an example)	Triborder workshop with other projects and A0s → in collaboration with PP08 and PP09	Other scientific and development projects that deal with climate change in the tri-border region.	Present Climate_CRICES and showcase the dashboard to other regional research and development projects to find out synergies with these.
26.02.2026	Online, 1 hour, in German	Eine Stunde fürs Klima (see above)	Saxonian municipalities, climate change	Demonstrate the dashboard and solicit feedback

Date	Duration and modality	Name/type of interaction	Target audience	Aim
	-		adaptation managers, and companies that plan interventions	about its usefulness to the users → see workshop report

2) Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes

Participants are generally aware of the importance of climate change adaptation but perceive significant structural constraints that limit implementation at the municipal level. Adaptation is not primarily seen as a lack of recognition of the problem, but rather as a challenge of resources, institutional conditions, and practical feasibility. Respondents indicate that municipalities often operate under tight financial and staffing conditions, while at the same time facing increasing responsibilities related to climate policy. In addition, the absence of strong legal mandates and the limited prioritisation of adaptation in political decision-making create uncertainty and slow progress.

Overall, participants identify several key areas that shape the current situation:

- **Resource constraints:** Limited funding and staff capacities make it difficult for municipalities to plan and implement adaptation measures.
- **Institutional and governance challenges:** Weak legal requirements and fragmented responsibilities reduce incentives and clarity for action.
- **Knowledge and decision-making gaps:** Decision-makers sometimes lack sufficient understanding of climate risks and the long-term implications of different policy choices.

At the same time, the responses reflect a constructive and solution-oriented attitude. Participants highlight the need for **more practical support to translate awareness into action**, particularly through:

- better access to reliable, locally relevant data and decision-support tools,
- strengthened technical and interdisciplinary capacities within administrations,
- improved coordination across governance levels and sectors, and
- stronger engagement with local communities, supported by clear examples of successful and cost-effective adaptation measures.

Overall, the findings point to a stakeholder group that is engaged and aware of climate risks but seeks clearer guidance, practical tools, and enabling conditions to advance climate adaptation in practice.

3) Definition of the working pilot roadmap: an operational plan for each region defining the scope of work in the next phase.

a) Identification of the specific climate change impacts to be analysed (heat and drought, floods, biodiversity).

Participants identified **heat and drought as the most pressing climate risks**, followed by **heavy precipitation and flooding**. At the same time, **biodiversity impacts** were also recognised as an important concern in the broader climate adaptation context.

b) Indication of the specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.

The key reference documents to be targeted include the **Energy and Climate Change Programme Saxony 2021**, the **transboundary management plan for the Neisse River catchment**, and **related climate change management and adaptation plans from Poland, Germany, and the Czech Republic**.

Participants emphasised that the development of effective regional climate change adaptation plans requires practical enabling conditions rather than additional high-level strategies. Their responses point to a strong demand for tools, guidance, and cooperation structures that help municipalities translate awareness of climate risks into concrete planning and implementation steps. In particular, stakeholders stressed the importance of accessible information, structured early-stage planning support, and opportunities to learn from existing experiences and successful projects.

Key needs highlighted by participants include:

- **Practice-oriented data and decision-support tools:** Easily accessible data packages and analytical tools that help municipalities address priority risks such as heat, drought, flooding, and biodiversity loss.

- **Support for early planning phases:** Clear guidance for “phase zero” planning that enables municipalities to explore adaptation options and scope strategies before committing financial resources.
- **Learning from existing experiences:** Short, evidence-based case examples and cost-benefit insights from implemented adaptation projects to support local decision-making.
- **Capacity building and peer exchange:** Opportunities for peer-learning through workshops, communities of practice, and exchanges between municipalities and practitioners.

Participants also stressed the importance of **strengthening cooperation structures in the region**, particularly in cross-border contexts. They highlighted opportunities to improve coordination and joint action through:

- harmonised principles and simplified data exchange,
- shared contact infrastructures and thematic networks,
- cross-border and regional adaptation strategies, and
- cooperation frameworks such as Euroregional partnerships and EU programmes (e.g. INTERREG).

Overall, participants’ contributions suggest that the region would benefit from **practical tools, knowledge exchange, and collaborative governance structures** that support municipalities in developing locally tailored climate adaptation plans.

c. Analysis of participants' expectations and needs regarding digital tools.

The survey results suggest several **needs regarding digital tools for climate adaptation planning**. Participants value dashboards and similar tools primarily as **communication and justification instruments**, indicating a demand for digital platforms that help clearly present and defend adaptation measures to decision-makers, politicians, and the public. At the same time, respondents highlight the importance of tools that provide **analytical insights and added professional value**, supporting the development and refinement of municipal climate adaptation strategies through accessible data and comparative information.

However, the responses also point to a need for **stronger integration of digital tools into everyday administrative workflows**. While the dashboard is perceived as strategically useful, participants indicate that its operational usability for routine planning, reporting, and coordination could be improved. Overall, stakeholders expressed a need for digital solutions that not only provide strategic information and visualisations but are also **easy to integrate into daily administrative practice**, enabling municipalities to use them as part of their regular planning and decision-making processes.

4) Plan for addendum integration and identification of data application areas

PP07 intends to co-develop a tri-border addendum jointly with PP08 (UPWr) and PP09 (UJEP), focused on the Neisse/Nysa catchment context and on avoiding maladaptation caused by cross-border governance, methodological, and data inconsistencies. This is consistent with the project logic where addenda can function as technical, evidence-first documents supporting (not replacing) existing strategies and plans, with flexible uptake pathways depending on the institutional mandate of associated partners.

To strengthen the uptake of climate adaptation tools and knowledge, participants highlighted the need to reduce language barriers by providing systematic translations of key materials, tools, and guidance so they are accessible across regions and user groups. They also emphasised the importance of increasing visibility and awareness of existing initiatives, tools, and good practices, as many potentially useful solutions remain insufficiently known among practitioners. In addition, establishing a community of users was seen as valuable for enabling exchange, peer learning, and feedback, thereby supporting the continuous improvement and wider adoption of climate adaptation approaches.

PP08

- **Activities performed**

Bilateral consultations (IRT, MKOOpZ)

Targeted discussions on planning cycles, policy context, and practical expectations towards the dashboard and methods for the piloting phase (incl. how results can be used in regional policy work).

Interactive sessions and feedback collection during thematic events (conference-based micro-trainings)

Shortened “dashboard logic” walk-through (data sources, indicators, risk logic, limitations) combined with structured feedback collection:

- IOŚ conference (23.10) - Google Forms
Audience with direct links to adaptation planning review processes and regional/local authorities.
- “Buildings in the Climate of the Future” (UPWr, 12.12) - Mentimeter
Event used to collect expert input, especially relevant for biodiversity-related expectations and interpretation needs.

- Localience / Akademia Pożarnicza (12.02) - Google Forms
Event focused on impacts of extreme weather and operational response context (crisis management, response, recovery).

Participation in stakeholder events organised by other institutions

Introductory project and dashboard explanations during workshop blocks and informal discussions, also used to refine stakeholder mapping and improve “reaching the right people” inside larger organisations.

Workshops and consultations:

- IRT (30.01) - meeting of the Advisory Team for Lower Silesian Water Policy (DPW).
- Markersdorf workshop (Euroregion Neisse, 21.10) - participation together with German partners.
- Public consultations of Wrocław’s Municipal Adaptation Plan update.

Online events organised / co-organised

- Joint tri-border kick-off (November 2025) with regional and national institutions and related projects.
- Stakeholder workshop (27.02). Workshop focused on practical expectations towards the dashboard and pilot analyses.

Preparation of training materials

- Training package for consortium partners (reusable in their own training activities):
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RZ4o0u0e9nkXICp89uY_9k5tj0gz1jBC?usp=drive_link
- Supporting microlearning and gamified materials introducing key terms and dashboard logic.

- **Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes**

Participants typically showed high interest in data-driven planning, but uneven baseline capacity to work with climate datasets and scenarios independently (especially in smaller municipalities and institutions with limited analytical staff).

Recurrent barriers were related to:

- limited awareness of existing data sources and access routes,
- limited skills for interpretation and uncertainty handling,
- unclear competences and responsibilities across institutions (strongly visible in the crisis-management audience).

Once the dashboard logic (modules, indicator selection, data provenance, limitations) was explained, stakeholders were able to provide more precise, actionable feedback, suggesting that short, structured onboarding significantly increases readiness to use dashboard outputs.

- **Definition of the working pilot roadmap**

- **specific climate change impacts to be analysed**

The pilot roadmap keeps all three core thematic areas in scope:

- Heat and drought (frequently prioritised, including compound effects)
- Flooding (incl. flash floods and torrential rainfall-driven events - prioritised by local administration)
- Biodiversity impacts (strong interest from expert audiences, highlighting the need for interpretation support)

- **Specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.**

- The regional policy reference points for the Lower Silesian context are Dolnośląska Polityka Wodna (Lower Silesian Water Policy) and Climate neutrality action plan for the Lower Silesian Voivodeship used as the main “entry point” for discussing practical measures and policy alignment (IRT as key stakeholder).
- River Basin Management Plan for the Oder River Basin District (Polish Water Authority is not the formal AP in the project).

Transboundary context (MKOOpZ and WP are not the formal AP in the project)

- RBMP for the international Oder river basin district.
- Flood Risk Management Plan for the international Oder river basin district.
- **Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools**

Across Forms-based feedback (and qualitative event discussions), the most requested functionalities and needs were:

- visualisation of indicators and projections as a core requirement,
 - scenario support and comparative views (across time horizons, scenarios, and areas),
 - reporting/export features to use outputs in planning documents and presentations,
 - guidance on interpretation (especially uncertainty, multi-scenario logic, and how to translate results into decisions),
 - combining multiple sources and making provenance transparent,
 - region-to-region comparability to support benchmarking and discussion with decision-makers.
- **Plan for addendum integration**

Integration pathway: modular addendum components aligned with DPW and municipal planning workflows

Target users for integration:

Main: IRT as AP

Additional possible interested parties:

- municipalities (including those outsourcing parts of adaptation plan preparation),
- sectoral stakeholders (crisis management, water management, biodiversity protection).

Polish Waters and The International Commission on the Protection of the Oder against Pollution, who are responsible for the BRMP and the FRMP, are not the AP. They have strict timelines and rules for updating documents, so addressing their documents will be more relevant to institutions that use these plans.

- **Identification of data application areas**

Based on stakeholder feedback, the highest added value of climate data and dashboard outputs is expected in the following application areas:

- Monitoring and evaluation of impacts and measures (tracking effects over time).
- Risk identification and prioritisation (spatially explicit risk understanding, including local-scale perspective).
- Justification of investments and measures (evidence for decision-makers and funding applications).
- Action planning and reporting (planning documents, presentations, reporting outputs).
- Practical use of spatial layers and municipal-scale indicators (as the core “daily-use” dashboard layer).

Institution-specific focus:

- IRT (as key regional stakeholder and main integration entry point in Lower Silesia): transboundary catchment context and cross-border dependencies (need to understand upstream-downstream relations and avoid maladaptation driven by inconsistent approaches across the tri-border area).

Stakeholders also highlighted the need for practical, locally usable datasets presented in a spatial form (eg local-scale projections and risk maps), and for linking dashboard content with established reference sources used in practice (eg Klimada). (Recorded from Miro sticky-note inputs by the organiser; not included as text in the Miro PDF export.)

PP09

1. Activities performed + workshop reports link

During the pilot phase, the UJEP project team organised an online stakeholder pre-training workshop for the Liberec Region on 11 November 2025. The session brought together representatives of the regional authority, selected municipalities and the Regional Development Agency (ARR), together with the UJEP team. The workshop introduced the Climate_CRICES project strategy, explained the logic of the data dashboard, and collected feedback on practical use cases, data gaps and usability needs in regional and municipal adaptation planning, with specific attention to the Nisa River basin context and cross-border relevance.

In parallel, a training activity has been launched in the form of a webinar series running in January–February 2026, aimed at strengthening user capacity to interpret climate information and translate it into adaptation measures. Four one-hour webinars were organised, with 38 participants in total. Webinars were also recorded and published online ([YouTube](#)).

2. Assessment of knowledge level and attitudes:

The workshop and follow-up exchanges indicate clear progress in stakeholder understanding of both the overall project strategy and the intended role of the dashboard as an operational support tool for adaptation planning. At the same time, readiness to use the dashboard in everyday institutional practice is currently uneven. Stakeholders are positively disposed and interested in applying the tool, but their ability to do so depends on available time, basic data literacy, and user-friendly features such as clear metadata, easy filtering and reliable export options. Competencies related to interpreting indicators and linking them to concrete measures are generally present, but there is a notable need to strengthen scenario thinking and the practical use of climate projections for forecasting impacts. Overall attitudes were constructive and solution-oriented, with willingness to engage in testing and to contribute to data-related cooperation, especially where ARR can act as an intermediary between municipalities and the regional level.

The thematic webinars also provided participants with new practical knowledge of climate change adaptation. In the end-of-webinar questionnaire (Mentimeter), almost all participants stated that the webinar was useful and that they will apply the approaches in their work.

3. Definition of the working pilot roadmap: an operational plan for each region defining the scope of work in the next phase.

For the next phase, the operational pilot roadmap for the Liberec Region focuses on moving from introductory awareness to practical use and institutional embedding. The first steps are targeted dashboard testing with key users (ARR and selected municipality),

establishing a “data library” workflow that enables downloading, documenting and reusing datasets and indicators in the institution’s internal processes, and agreement on data maintenance and responsibilities. These steps should be supported by follow-up meetings with stakeholders to tailor outputs to their mandates, and creating addendums.

a. Identification of the specific climate change impacts to be analysed (heat and drought, floods, biodiversity).

Based on stakeholder input, the priority climate change impacts to be analysed in the pilot territory include flooding and heavy rainfall as the most immediate concern, reflecting risks of intense precipitation, flash floods, overloaded drainage systems, and impacts on settlements and infrastructure, particularly in river basin and urban contexts. Heat and rising temperatures form another key area, including heatwaves, urban heat island effects and related health impacts. Drought and low water availability were also highlighted, with expected consequences for ecosystems, agriculture and forestry as well as competing water demands. Finally, stakeholders emphasised ecosystem and biodiversity impacts and noted that biodiversity aspects are often less systematically captured in current planning; strengthening the evidence base in this area is therefore considered an important analytical priority.

b. Indication of the specific climate adaptation plan that serves as the reference document for the given region.

The pilot work is anchored in existing adaptation strategies and planning documents used by the Liberec Region and participating municipalities. The main reference policy is the Action plan for adaptation to climate change in the Liberec region (2021). The dashboard is therefore positioned as a supporting evidence tool that helps update and operationalise this document, rather than replacing it. Another concrete reference discussed for practical application and potential improvement is the municipal climate adaptation strategy of Hrádek nad Nisou, including its old risk/vulnerability assessment, which offers an immediate entry point for testing how dashboard outputs can support revisions. In addition, Plan of the sub-basin of the Lusatian Neisse and other tributaries of the Oder were analysed for potential triborder addendum.

c. Analysis of participants expectations and needs regarding digital tools.

Stakeholders expect digital tools to be practical and “usable under real conditions”, meaning that the dashboard should not only visualise information but allow straightforward comparison across territories, provide reliable exports for reports and strategies, and ensure transparent metadata describing what each dataset represents and how it can be reused. There is also demand for a curated collection of datasets (“data

library") and, where possible, connections to external systems such as APIs. Beyond technical features, participants stressed organisational needs: clear responsibilities for data management, regular updates and long-term ownership, so that the tool becomes part of routine planning rather than a project output used only temporarily. A further expectation concerns capacity building - targeted trainings are needed to strengthen interpretation of indicators, use of projections, and communication of adaptation measures. The overall conclusion is that the highest value will be achieved when technical usability, data governance and training are developed together.

Plan for addendum integration:

The pilot results will be integrated into existing strategic documents primarily through evidence-based updates and improvements of current sections, rather than replacing them. Findings from stakeholder cooperation and pilot analyses can feed revisions of risk and vulnerability assessments, strengthen the prioritisation of adaptation measures based on consistent indicators, and improve monitoring and evaluation frameworks through better-defined baselines and measurable targets. In practical terms, integration can be supported by providing recommended indicator sets, referencing dashboard data and guidelines sources in annexes or data sections, and establishing update routines that keep strategic documents aligned with evolving evidence. Where required, these updates can also help institutions respond to new or changing regulatory expectations by providing a transparent and traceable data basis for adaptation planning.

Identification of data application areas:

For the involved institutions, climate data and dashboard outputs offer the highest added value in strategic planning and policy updates, where evidence is needed to justify priorities and translate them into actionable measures. They are equally valuable for risk and vulnerability assessments, enabling more consistent assessment over time and across territories. Another key application area is spatial and urban planning, including targeting of green infrastructure, cooling measures and retention solutions, and supporting decisions on zoning and infrastructure resilience. Flood risk management, emergency preparedness and broader water management are also central, especially in contexts where heavy rainfall and drought interact and require integrated solutions. Stakeholders also see a strong benefit in strengthening biodiversity and ecosystem considerations through better indicators and evidence. Finally, climate data can support funding and project preparation by improving the rationale for investment decisions and grant applications, and it can enhance communication with decision-makers and the public by providing clear, visual and credible information.

LP01 + PP02

Pilot Veneto

27 January 2026

Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: Online meeting of Climate_CRICES project

Region/Country: Veneto

Date & location: January 27, 2026

Organising partner: Regione Veneto and ARPA Veneto

Participants (institutions + short role description): 35 participant technicians from various Offices of the Veneto Region, ARPAV, Land Reclamation Consortia and from local Drinking Water Management Bodies.

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

Why the workshop was organised.

The workshop was organised in order to Continue and consolidate the engagement of Veneto public administration officials who, during the first meeting, have expressed interest in the opportunities offered by the Climate_CRICES project.

How it connects to Climate_CRICES.

The speakers' interventions were aimed at:

- Increase Veneto public administration officials' awareness of climate change-related issues;
- Increase technicians' knowledge of the availability and accessibility of historical weather and climate data, particularly indicators useful for characterizing droughts and heat waves;
- Increase technicians' knowledge of the meaning and accessibility of data/indicators relating to end-of-the-century climate projections;
- Foster contacts that provide useful information for the Climate_CRICES project's activities from users, including through the definition of specific climate products and services necessary for institutional activities.

How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.

During the workshop, some specific needs emerged from some technicians in terms of accessibility to weather and climate data.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

The event was promoted through the following invitation letter:

Dear Sir/Madam,

Managing the impacts of climate change is an increasingly urgent matter, requiring skills and tools capable of helping politicians, managers, and public and private operators prevent and mitigate the consequences on our territory and our economy.

We hereby invite you to participate in the online meeting to be held on

January 27, 2026, from 9:30 a.m. to 12:15 p.m.

to continue our training program within the Climate_CRICES project (https://www.interregcentral.eu/projects/climate_crices/), which aims to develop and promote tools for activities and policies for adapting to climate change, with particular reference to the issues of drought and heatwaves, floods, and biodiversity conservation.

The project, led by the Veneto Region and technical partner ARPAV, is composed of public partners representing Piedmont (Italy), Germany (Saxony); Poland, Czech Republic, Hungary, and Croatia.

With this meeting, we would like to delve into the tools available to local public operators, both at the strategic level (SRACC) and at the operational level (project dashboards and other regional tools).

The Veneto Region has sent a registration form to interested entities and technicians to be filled out:

Reminder emails were sent in the days leading up to the event.

The screenshot shows a Google Forms registration page titled "Meeting online del progetto Climate_CRICES – 27 gennaio 2026". The form includes a header with the project name and date, a "Modulo di registrazione" label, and a user email field (francesco.rech@arpa.veneto.it) with a "Cambia account" link. Below this is a "Non condiviso" status and a note: "* Indica una domande obbligatorie". The form contains four required text input fields: "Ente rappresentato *", "Nome e Cognome del partecipante *", "Posizione organizzativa nell'ente rappresentato *", and "Indirizzo dell'Ente *". At the bottom, there are "Invia" and "Cancella modulo" buttons, along with a footer containing Google Modules branding and a disclaimer: "Questo modulo è stato creato all'interno di SndriniRoberto - Contatta il proprietario del modulo. Questo modulo sembra sospetto? Segnala".

To encourage participation, the meeting was held online. Participants were provided with the link (<https://meet.google.com/prp-kegb-fvt>)

The meeting agenda was as follows:

Timetable	Topic	Speaker
09:15 - 09:30	Registration and Connection	
09:30 - 09:45	Opening remarks and brief presentation of the Climate_CRICES project	RV ICT e Dir. Ambiente L. De Pietro/P. Giandon
09:45 - 10:00	The Climate_CRICES project dashboard Progress of work and prospects	RV ICT - M. Tegon
10:00 - 10:20	Climate change in the Veneto region with particular reference to drought and heat waves	ARPAV-F. Zecchini
10:20 - 10:40	Access to historical data and future projections (data available via the CLINE platform)	ARPAV-G. Massaro
10:40 - 10:55	Use of data in ARPAV bulletins	ARPAV-F. Rech
10:55 - 11:10	Break	
11:10 - 11:30	The SRACC and intervention measures in Veneto to mitigate the effects of climate change	RV - P. Giandon
11:30 - 12:00	Discussion with participants based on the questionnaire distributed	RV - V. Vonghia
12:00 - 12:15	Conclusion of the meeting and next steps	RV - M. Tegon

The workshop was structured in four phases:

- 1) After the opening greetings and an overview of the Project, supported by a presentation video, a short video tutorial of the dashboard was shown, explaining how to access it from the Veneto Region portal, the Project website, and the dashboard itself. The dashboard was not discussed in depth, as it is currently still in a provisional and evolving phase.
- 2) The workshop then moved on to more technical presentations, which lasted just under an hour.

During the first presentation, the indicators used for climate monitoring of droughts and heatwaves were illustrated;

With the second presentation was explored the CliNE (North-East Climate) platform, which collects historical data from ARPAV weather stations and climate projections up to 2100 for various models and emissions scenarios. The data available are presented in the form of maps and time series, with the possibility of processing such as moving averages and trends, and is freely downloadable.

The third presentation listed and illustrated a series of bulletins and reports produced by ARPAV, available online for the general public or targeted to specific audiences, again related to the topics of drought and heatwaves.

- 3) After a brief intermission, the key policy, the Regional Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (SRACC), was presented, outlining its lines of action and the process of developing and approving it.
- 4) Finally, the responses to the questionnaire, specially designed and administered for the first time during the workshop, were analyzed. This questionnaire will, however, be re-administered to different audiences. The purpose of the questionnaire is to gather crucial feedback from key stakeholders, in order to refining regional climate adaptation strategies. At the end of the meeting, the importance of dialogue with stakeholders was reiterated, and the next steps in the engagement process were outlined.

After each presentation, there was time for interaction with stakeholders.

These presentations in Italian are reported in the link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wScdHoGt5GevmtrkwEwFMtCmZttSuYUv?usp=sharing>

Participants were sent a finalized questionnaire before the meeting.

18 participants answered the questionnaire.

Of these 18 participants, 6 were technicians from various offices of the Veneto Region, 5 were technicians from land reclamation consortia and 6 were technicians from local drinking water management bodies.

Nome dell'Organizzazione / Ente

18 risposte

Tipologia di Stakeholder

18 risposte

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

Quali tra i seguenti fenomeni climatici ritiene rappresentino la minaccia maggiore per il settore o il territorio di sua competenza nei prossimi 5-10 anni?

18 risposte

To the multiple-choice question: **Which of the following climate phenomena do you believe pose the greatest threat to your sector or region over the next 5-10 years?**

We have the following answers:

17 out of 50 responses highlighted the importance of water scarcity and prolonged drought;

16 responses highlighted the importance of floods and hydrogeological instability;

9 responses highlighted the importance of extreme events;

4 responses concerned heat waves;

4 responses emphasized the importance of sea level rise.

The importance of floods and extreme weather events is undeniable, and regional authorities are already actively working in these areas, especially after the flood of November 2010.

However, especially for stakeholders such as Land Reclamation Consortia (agricultural irrigation water) and Drinking Water Management Agencies, drought represents a significant impact that must be addressed in planning and in operational management.

In che misura la sua organizzazione ha già subito danni economici o operativi riconducibili a eventi climatici estremi negli ultimi 5 anni?

18 risposte

An additional question posed by the questionnaire was: **To what extent has your organization already suffered economic or operational damage attributable to extreme weather events in the last 5 years?**

None of the participants responded that they had not suffered damage from extreme weather events.

16 people reported moderate impacts but with damage and service interruptions;

2 participants state that their organizations have suffered minor damages and 1 reports, on the contrary, significant economic damages.

(the questionnaire was a multiple choice questionnaire with a total of 19 answers, perhaps one of the participants suffered damages of different degrees in different events)

One participant also reported the effects of extreme events on biodiversity (an effect difficult to quantify).

One participant reported the effects of water scarcity on irrigation costs (energy consumption).

Was also asked: What is the progress of your organization/institution in adopting a formal climate adaptation plan?

Qual è lo stato di avanzamento della sua organizzazione/ente nell'adozione di un piano formale di adattamento climatico?

18 risposte

8 responses indicate that the institution has defined an adaptation strategy but has not yet adopted it.

6 responses indicated that participant's organizations have operational and monitored adaptation measures in place. Only one participant also indicated that the measures adopted include a drought management plan.

1 participant reported that their organization has not addressed the topic of climate change adaptation while 5 responses reported that their organizations are starting to assess the risks.

4.2 Identified Barriers

(Data, Indicators, Governance)

Quali sono i principali ostacoli che impediscono l'attuazione di misure di adattamento efficaci? (Selezionare massimo 2)

18 risposte

To the multiple-choice question: **What are the main obstacles preventing the implementation of effective adaptation measures?**

- 11 out of 33 responses highlighted the lack of dedicated financial resources;
- 9 report the difficulty of coordination between different bodies;
- 5 highlighted the bureaucratic and regulatory complexity;
- 5 reported the uncertainty about future climate data at the local scale;
- 2 responses concerned the lack of technical skills;
- 1 response concerned the lack of long-term strategies.

Effective interventions to manage water scarcity or excess water (floods) in a densely populated area require complex structural interventions that require adequate financial resources and also require significant planning and authorization efforts. Therefore, the importance technicians attach to the issue of available financial resources is understandable.

The difficulties of coordination between different bodies are a second important issue that is affected by the complexity of the water cycle but also by the fact that in Italy the planning, authorization and management jurisdiction are often divided.

Although the Region and ARPAV have worked in recent years to make available data on climate projections for the end of the century with a particular focus on the Veneto region, evidently this information is not always known or clear to the technicians of the local authorities.

The questionnaire also asked: **How do you rate the current level of coordination between the Veneto Region and local stakeholders on the topic of adaptation?**

Come valuta l'attuale livello di coordinamento tra la Regione Veneto e gli stakeholder locali sul tema dell'adattamento?

18 risposte

only 1 participant answered Excellent, 8

8 responded "good but could be improved" (politically correct), 3 responded "sufficient," and six responded "insufficient."

These responses likely highlight a growing need for local authorities to support adaptation efforts, which the Region has not always provided, or at least has not provided quickly enough.

4.3 Identified Needs

(Technical, Organisational, Practical)

Participants were asked: **What types of interventions do you consider to be priorities for the regional territory?**

The question was multiple choice.

14 responses signal the importance of the "Grey" infrastructure (dikes, retention basins, barriers);

10 responses signal the importance of the Nature-Based Solutions (e.g., reforestation, wetland restoration);

7 answers were about the importance of Digitalization and Early Warning Systems;

12 answers were about the Review of urban planning and land use;

4 answers were about the Training and awareness-raising among citizens and businesses.

Among the aspects reported directly by the questionnaire compilers are:

- Interconnection of water networks, implementation of compensation volumes, rationalization of water withdrawals, reduction of losses in Network;
- Validated climate projection platform for drafting an Adaptation Plan;
- Systems for collecting rainwater for irrigation purposes to reduce the use of drinking water.

Most of the participants (14) underlined the importance of structural hydraulic interventions as a very important adaptation measure for the Veneto region, but great importance is also given (12) to territorial planning capable of regulating land use.

Among the indications provided independently by the participants, 2 directly concern the risk of drought and refer to the optimisation of water use and the reduction of losses from the aqueducts.

Stakeholders were asked an open-ended question: **If you had to indicate a single absolute priority for the Veneto Climate Agenda 2026-2030, what would it be?**

15 responses were obtained:

- 1) Effective regulation on the reuse of treated water and coordination of SII ((Integrated water system) management bodies with land reclamation consortia and other stakeholders.
- 2) Extreme events.
- 3) Retention basins and stormwater collection basins.
- 4) Green infrastructure.
- 5) Stop land consumption without exceptions and reclaim abandoned sites, restoring them to nature.
- 6) Protect water resources for human use, plan investments to counter extreme events.
- 7) Shared and validated climate projections.
- 8) Water saving.
- 9) Recognize irrigation as a mitigation (probably the correct term is adaptation) tool for the effects of climate change.
- 10) Investments in strategic infrastructure.
- 11) Development of operational and sectoral plans for adaptation to climate change.
- 12) Minimization of flood risk.
- 13) Multifunctional reservoir plan.
- 14) Development of operational plans for adaptation to climate change for the various affected sectors.
- 15) Adaptation to rising temperatures

At least 6 out of 15 answers are directly related to water management in conditions of scarcity. Furthermore, 4 answers explicitly refer to the importance of planning, while a further answer talks about regulation of water use and coordination between management bodies.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

(Shared datasets, synergies, potential working groups etc)

The workshop allowed LP and PP_01 to assess stakeholders' initial level of knowledge and attitudes regarding climate change, available tools, and regional adaptation policies.

Participants demonstrated a good awareness of regional climate impacts, particularly drought and water scarcity, consistent with their professional profiles, which are primarily related to water resource management and land reclamation consortia. However, they noted a lack of complete understanding of the extent of the climate changes underway and limited immediate availability of consolidated data and indicators. Participants expressed a need for a better data accessibility.

Regarding climate tools and data, some participants were already familiar with some of the platforms and products presented, while for many, the meeting represented a first opportunity for discovery, generating interest and requests for further information.

Regarding adaptation strategies, it emerged that, although the adoption of formal plans by every institution is not mandatory, several entities, particularly land reclamation consortia, have already adopted operational tools to address climate impacts, often anticipating the development of structured strategies in response to concrete and immediate needs.

The attitudes that emerged indicate a high level of interest in using weather and climate data in daily work and a positive perception of the usefulness of digital tools in supporting decision-making. The need for greater data integration between regions was also highlighted, given the supraregional nature of river basins, given the current fragmentation of information management and sharing systems.

The most significant interactions involved technical profiles, particularly water resource managers. Finally, initial findings from the questionnaire confirm a strong demand for institutional action, even through complex or potentially unpopular measures, to effectively address the impacts of climate change.

During the workshop the dashboard was presented only briefly and was not considered central by participants; greater interest was shown in data platforms such as CliNE and the available operational information. The technicians present, particularly those involved in water resources management, demonstrated excellent skills in interpreting climate indicators, maps, time series, and future scenarios.

Discussions revealed the interest of some entities (Land Reclamation Consortia) in accessing hydro-meteorological data for river basins crossing two regions. This entirely logical request conflicts with regional land management, monitoring systems, and databases approach. The issue is particularly relevant for land reclamation consortia operating in the Adige, Brenta, Livenza, Lemene, and Tagliamento river basins.

Data analysis for a trans-regional area has a climatological aspect (monthly rainfall distribution, differences from the average, etc.) for planning purposes, and an operational aspect aimed at assessing the current situation in real time.

This issue was not considered in the Climate_CRICES project. It is not easy to solve, given the organization of regional entities. However, we could propose interventions to address the problem or at least take it into account in future regional planning.

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

Based on the interactions with participants, the climate impacts considered to be priority were drought and floods. The importance of floods and extreme weather events is undeniable, and regional authorities are already actively working in these areas, especially after the flood of November 2010. However, especially for stakeholders such as Land Reclamation Consortia (agricultural irrigation water) and Drinking Water Management Agencies, drought represents a significant impact that must be addressed in planning and in operational management.

The problems of drought and heat waves are considered by the regional strategy for adaptation to climate change (SRACC) but are less known and less studied than the problems caused by excess water and are problems that, with the increase in temperatures, risk becoming more relevant both for their magnitude and for their duration.

5.2 Processes that need testing

It is necessary to intensify and detail the dialogue with stakeholders to understand exactly the type of interaction needed during the pilot phase.

In particular, it is necessary to understand what type of weather and climate data is needed, how quickly it should be updated, and in what formats.

It is necessary to understand what type of stakeholder's training may be useful or necessary to enable access and use of weather and climate data to support the operational activities of the technical offices.

5.3 Limitations to consider

ARPAV has good capabilities for processing climate indicators in various formats (numbers, tables, graphs, and maps). However, it has limited capabilities for making this data accessible in an organized manner to potential users.

The Climate_CRICES project Dashboard is not a suitable tool for visualizing and managing georeferenced data.

It could, however, become a tool to direct stakeholders in a rational and orderly manner towards directories that allow the download of the necessary data.

The possibility of linking the climatological data base via the Dashboard must be carefully analyzed and the limited updating capacity of the platform in the future must also be better considered.

In a nutshell: match the dashboard usage with the stakeholders' needs, also considering what we can technically do in the time available.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

The workshop contacts highlighted the need for supra-regional weather and climate data for operators managing territories near regional borders.

Water resource managers also expressed interest in the reliability and accessibility of long-term or seasonal forecasts.

Those topic are too complex to address in this project, but the needs are real.

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

It is necessary to give more space to stakeholder interaction by finalizing activities regarding data provision and training on the use of data and indicators. Therefore, specific needs and the possibility of implementing equally specific training activities must be considered.

6. Annexes

Reference documents cited in the text.

PP03 CSI Piemonte Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: DATI E ADATTAMENTO CLIMATICO - L'approccio pratico del progetto CLIMATE CRICES (DATA AND CLIMATE ADAPTATION - The practical approach of CLIMATE CRICES project)

Region / Country: Piedmont/Italy

Date & location: 19th November 2025

Organising partner: CSI Piemonte

Participants (institutions + short role description):

- Mariaelena Nicoella, Piedmont Region Environmental Agency - Stakeholder
- Francesco Gresta, Piedmont Region, Agriculture and Food Department - Stakeholder
- Emanuele Possiedi, Piedmont Region, Agriculture and Food Department - Stakeholder
- Federico Spanna, Piedmont Region, Agriculture and Food Department - Stakeholder
- Federica Ravizza, Politecnico di Torino - Stakeholder
- Valentina Santoro, Politecnico di Torino - Stakeholder
- Lorenzo Serra Bellini, Politecnico di Torino - Stakeholder
- Guglielmo Ricciardi - Scientific advisor
- Marta Ellena - Scientific advisor

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- Why the workshop was organised.
- How it connects to Climate_CRICES.
- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.

The workshop was organised to strengthen regional capacity on climate data use and develop a shared understanding of how the Climate_CRICES dashboard can support climate adaptation planning in Piedmont. It aimed to:

- introduce core climate-change concepts and terminology;
- present the logic, data sources, and key indicators integrated in the Climate_CRICES dashboard;
- offer a practical, hands-on session on navigating indicators relevant for agriculture, water, and territorial planning;
- stimulate structured dialogue among regional stakeholders on data needs, barriers, and opportunities for collaboration.

Its results directly inform the refinement of the dashboard and contribute to identifying priority themes for forthcoming Pilot Actions under Climate_CRICES.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

The workshop followed the agenda defined in the official programme

Programma_Workshop_Climate_CRICES.

Format: participatory, in-person with remote access; mix of presentations, guided discussion, and a practical dashboard exercise.

Module structure:

- Module 1 - Climate change fundamentals:

Presented by climate researchers. It covered global and regional climate trends, concepts such as risk, vulnerability, scenarios (GCM-RCM-local), differences between mitigation and adaptation, and sector-specific impacts with a focus on agriculture.

- Module 2 - The Climate_CRICES data logic:

Introduction to data sources (Copernicus, national meteorological services, ARPA datasets), indicator rationale, and existing limitations.

- Module 3 - Practical session on the Climate_CRICES dashboard:

Hands-on exploration of heat, drought, flood, biodiversity, and agriculture-related indicators; identification of locally relevant metrics; mini-plenary feedback.

Tools & materials: slide deck, dashboard interface, shared board for reflections, short self-assessment questionnaire.

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

Stakeholders highlighted the importance of high-quality, spatially resolved indicators to inform agricultural adaptation, water management, territorial planning, and regional strategies. Discussions emphasised:

- The need for more physiologically meaningful indicators for agriculture (e.g., temperature threshold exceedances rather than absolute averages).
- The relevance of including forestry (not only agroforestry) for both adaptation and mitigation due to its function as a carbon sink.
- The importance to include hydrological fluxes as climate information within the dashboard

- The importance of soil, both as a water-storage medium and as a component of biological fertility, with implications for drought resilience and long-term productivity.
- The value of linking climate data with local agronomic knowledge and planning tools already used by regional departments.

Stakeholders appreciated the dashboard's potential but stressed the need for clearer guidance on interpretation and integration into decision processes.

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

(ranking and short explanation)

Based on plenary reflections and indicator exploration:

- **Heat stress.** Identified as a major threat for crops and rural labour. Stakeholders requested indicators capturing critical temperature exceedances due to their direct physiological impacts.
- **Agricultural and ecological drought** Increasing evapotranspiration and reduced spring-summer precipitation were considered central risks affecting yields, soil moisture, and water management.

4.2 Identified Barriers

(Data, Indicators, Governance)

- **Data barriers:** scarcity of threshold-based indicators; limited availability of fine-scale soil metrics; varying temporal coverage across datasets.
- **Indicator barriers:** need for sector-specific metrics (heat thresholds, phenological indicators, crop-specific sensitivity); insufficient representation of forestry.
- **Governance barriers:** fragmentation between agricultural, forestry, and environmental datasets; limited integration of climate services in routine decision-making; gaps in data literacy.

4.3 Identified Needs

(Technical, Organisational, Practical)

Technical:

- enhancement of heat-stress and drought indicators relevant for agriculture;
- inclusion of forestry-related metrics;
- improved soil data (organic matter, water retention, biological activity);
- clearer documentation and interpretation guidelines.

Organisational:

- structured cooperation between regional units (agriculture, environment, forestry);
- sustained capacity-building pathways;
- clearer workflows for integrating dashboard outputs into planning.

Practical:

- user support during early adoption;
- examples of dashboard-informed decisions;
- iterative refinement based on real operational needs.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

(Shared datasets, synergies, potential working groups etc)

Stakeholders expressed interest in:

- sharing regional datasets (soil, crop calendars, local hydrological measurements);
- joint development of sector-specific indicators (agriculture, forestry, soil health);
- testing cross-department workflows for data-driven planning;
- collaborating with universities on methodological development and validation.

The workshop fostered constructive science-policy exchange, strengthening the foundation for co-developed solutions.

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

- Improvement of threshold-based agricultural heat indicators.
- Integration of forestry and agroforestry within adaptation dashboards.
- Development of soil-related indicators for drought and fertility.
- Strengthening interdepartmental data governance.

5.2 Processes that need testing

- Step-by-step integration of climate indicators in agricultural planning and regional strategies.
- Multi-source data fusion (regional datasets + CRICES indicators).
- Co-validation with practitioners and field experts.

5.3 Limitations to consider

- Heterogeneous data availability across sub-regions.
- Limited granularity of some soil and hydrological variables.
- Need for user training during the early phases of dashboard adoption.
- Legend closed to the graphics
- Glossary
- Connections through APIs to collect data from ARPA, in order to have the indicator calculated once and not repeated
- Increase the possibility to search text
- URL field
- Standardized index with anomalies
- Underline through the analysis which are the most critical areas and interventions

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

- A pilot on heat stress thresholds for key regional crops, co-developed with agricultural services.
- A pilot integrating forest and agroforestry indicators to assess adaptation-mitigation synergies.
- A pilot on soil moisture and biological fertility as cross-sector indicators for drought resilience.

5.5 Recommendations

- Expand collaboration with regional technical units and research institutions.
- Prioritise development of threshold-based, sector-specific indicators.
- Ensure continuity of capacity building for effective uptake of the dashboard.
- Strengthen data governance and interoperability.
- For a decision makers should be interested to see their level of risk and the comparison with the national risk level

6. Annexes

- participant list
- photos/screenshots
- notes/boards

- Voting results

PP04 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: Climate_CRICES Training Activity Workshop

Region/Country: Burgenland, Austria

Date & location: 19 November 2025, Research Burgenland, Eisenstadt

Organising partner: Research Burgenland GmbH (PP04)

Participants (institutions + short role description):

Representatives from:

- Provincial administration
- KLAR! Regions National Park Neusiedler See
- ARGE Nature Parks
- Tourism sector
- Research and advisory institutions

Participants represented regional governance, biodiversity management, tourism, adaptation planning and research.

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- Why the workshop was organised.
The workshop was organised to present the updated Climate_CRICES dashboard and collect structured feedback from end users regarding its functionality and application.
- How it connects to Climate-CRICES.
The session directly supported the project objective of strengthening institutional capacity to use a data-driven dashboard for climate adaptation planning.
- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.
The feedback gathered informs the operational refinement of pilot testing, particularly regarding usability, indicator prioritisation and target-group orientation.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Presentation of climate change impacts in Burgenland

Project update and dashboard progress overview

Live demonstration of the dashboard

Structured feedback session

Final reflection round

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

Participants identified the following as priority risks for Burgenland:

1. Heat and drought

Participants highlighted heat stress and drought-related challenges as key priorities for Burgenland and stressed the need for clear, municipality-oriented information to support practical planning and communication.

2. Local heavy rainfall events

Stakeholders referred to local heavy rainfall events as a relevant risk and underlined the value of spatially clear data presentation to support local preparedness and decision-making.

3. Biodiversity related impacts

Participants discussed biodiversity impacts as highly relevant and pointed to current gaps in biodiversity data and expert input, which should be considered when further developing and applying the dashboard.

Overall, the workshop confirmed strong stakeholder interest in using the Climate-CRICES dashboard for practical, municipality-level climate adaptation planning. At the same time, participants highlighted the importance of a clear, targeted structure and prioritised indicators, and noted that biodiversity-related analyses would benefit from strengthened data availability and expert input.

4.2 Identified Barriers

Data and structure-related:

- High number of indicators
- Need for clearer dashboard structure
- Complex interconnections between indicators

Technical aspects:

- Importance of stable and browser-independent performance
- Need for a clear municipal-level entry point

4.3 Identified Needs

Technical needs:

- Two-level dashboard structure (basic and advanced level)
- Reduced and prioritised core indicators
- Municipal comparison functionality
- Search function

Organisational needs:

- Accompanying training sessions and guidance materials
- Clear differentiation between target groups

Practical needs:

- Simplified interface for political decision-makers
- Clear and prioritised visual presentation of data

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

- Inclusion of biodiversity expertise
- Engagement of thematic advisory bodies
- Use of dashboard outputs for awareness-raising in municipalities and protected areas

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

- Municipal-level heat and drought analysis
- Flood risk indicators
- Biodiversity-related data integration

5.2 Processes that need testing

- Simplified indicator selection
- Target-group-oriented dashboard logic
- Application of dashboard outputs in municipal planning workflows

5.3 Limitations to consider

- Availability and quality of biodiversity data
- Need for structured onboarding and support

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

Based on the inputs from the workshop, one proposed Pilot Action could focus on testing a simplified, municipality-oriented dashboard structure with a reduced set of core indicators (e.g., heat, drought and heavy rainfall). This pilot would demonstrate how a clearly prioritised indicator set, combined with a structured

entry point at municipal level, can support practical planning and decision-making processes.

A second Pilot Action could involve testing a two-level dashboard approach (basic and advanced view) with selected municipalities or stakeholder groups. The objective would be to assess how different user profiles—such as political decision-makers and technical staff—interact with prioritised indicators, comparison functions and search options, and how these features enhance usability and application in real planning contexts.

6. Recommendations (lesson learned)

The pilot phase should start with a clear municipal entry point and a reduced set of core indicators, potentially structured in a basic and an advanced level, to support different user groups. Participants also highlighted that practical application scenarios should reflect real planning needs (e.g., comparing municipalities and using searchable locations) and be accompanied by short guidance or training inputs to ensure consistent interpretation and use.

PP05 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title:

Region/Country: Central Danube, Hungary

Date & location: 11 December, online

Organising partner: PP05-CDDA

Participants (institutions + short role description):

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- Why the workshop was organised.

The aim of the workshop was to present the results of the Climate_CRICES to date, in particular the dashboard currently being developed as part of the project, to planning professionals actively involved in municipal-level planning in the region. The target group of the workshop was not municipal officials, but professionals who, as employees of consulting firms, assist municipalities in their climate change-related planning activities. There were two reasons for selecting this specific target group. On the one hand, we did not consider it appropriate to show the dashboard in its current state to its primary target group, i.e., municipal government employees. Secondly, employees in the consulting sector in the Middle Danube Region have the most background information for further developing the dashboard and expanding its professional input.

- How it connects to Climate_CRICES.

The workshop was organized as part of the Climate-CRICES project.

- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.

Among other things, the workshop discussed the information gaps that hinder the effective adaptation of municipalities in the region to climate change. In the Pilot Actions, we aim to develop practice-oriented solutions and easy-to-use planning tools for some of these gaps.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

The workshop was organized online.

Agenda:

- o **Local climate challenges:** heat, drought, floods, changes in biodiversity
- o **Data-driven decision-making:** presentation of the Climate_CRICES Dashboard
- o **Sharing experiences:** regional adaptation strategies and best practices

The workshop consisted of short introductory presentations on the above topics, followed by an interactive discussion, during which all participants had the opportunity to express their opinions on the given topic and make suggestions for further development of the dashboard and, more generally, for enhancing the professional support provided by Climate_CRICES.

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

The workshop participants considered drought and water shortage to be the most serious climate change-related challenges in the region. At the same time, they noted that this phenomenon is usually accompanied by heat waves in summer, which further exacerbate the devastating effects of drought due to increased evaporation. However, drought is not limited to summer; last winter, for example, was particularly dry. All of this has a serious impact on the region's wildlife, contributing to a decline in biodiversity. Overall, therefore, the most serious climate risk in the Middle Danube region is drought/water shortage, followed by an increase in the frequency of heat waves and, as a consequence of the former, a decline in biodiversity.

4.2 Identified Barriers

(1) According to workshop participants, it is confusing for municipal staff that databases containing climate parameters generally include several different future scenarios for the same phenomenon. The concept of uncertainty is difficult to understand for the primary target group, making them uncertain about the usability of the data.

(2) It is often the case that good practices and measures from other countries cannot be directly applied in the Hungarian context. When this has been attempted, the result has often been failure.

(3) Many decision-makers and farmers are not able to conduct in-depth data analysis.

(4) The workshop placed significant emphasis on the sustainability and long-term operation of the Climate_CRICES results, particularly of the dashboard. In Interreg projects, there is no mandatory maintenance period, so the future of the system largely depends on the partners' willingness to cooperate and on potential additional funding sources.

4.3 Identified Needs

The workshop participants identified the following as possible solutions to the above barriers.

(1) The dashboard should demonstrate that, based on recent decades, pessimistic climate scenarios are closer to current trends and should therefore be treated as the default (at least, this is the case in the Middle Danube region). In order to increase the motivation of local governments to plan for climate change adaptation, strong, attention-grabbing, "shocking" messages are needed.

(2) Attention-grabbing messages ("pop-ups") would be needed to indicate that adaptation measures must be tailored to local conditions. There was also a demand for the system to be able to identify similar municipalities (e.g., based on climatic, size-related, or agri-economic similarities), thereby supporting the search for relevant patterns. Although there are technical limitations due to the capabilities of Power BI, this proposal was considered important and should be forwarded to the partnership.

(3) It is recommended to formulate short, clear, visual, and narrative messages (e.g. in Hungary comparisons with the 2022 drought).

(4) Possible solutions for sustaining the project results:

- involvement of market actors (financing, ESG links),
- involvement of municipalities and county-level organizations as data providers,
- additional Interreg applications to further develop the platform.

Sustainability issues should also be addressed among project outputs (e.g., in the form of addenda or recommendations).

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

The workshop participants agreed that guidelines on the application of future climate scenarios are particularly important for local actors. Several databases and professional guidelines are available in Hungary to assist with this, and it would be important to collect them and display them together on a single platform. The dashboard is expected to be suitable for this function.

Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

Based on the results of the workshop, at least one of the pilot actions must address local drought prevention and management options. It is advisable to choose a pilot action that aims to raise widespread awareness of this type of project. Based on the experiences of the workshop participants, the greatest motivating factor for municipalities to implement climate adaptation measures is learning about the benefits of similar developments in their region.

When planning pilot actions, it is also important to focus on developing a methodology that is as easy to use as possible. In other words, the primary goal of pilot actions should not be to develop guidelines, but rather to create a directly usable template for a climate adaptation plan (e.g., a heatwave plan) that can be adapted to the needs of the municipality.

5.2 Processes that need testing

5.3 Limitations to consider

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

Based on the results of the workshop and the planning process so far, the following pilot action topics have been identified:

- Developing a template for a municipal heat and UV alert plan tailored to the specific characteristics of the Middle Danube Region, with instructions for use that also mention the dashboard as a data source
- Identifying innovative municipal-level rainwater management developments previously implemented in the Middle Danube Region, collecting experiences related to their planning, implementation, and local social acceptance, and formulating recommendations for overcoming the barriers that have arisen
- Identifying procedures that promote the adaptation of viticulture, which is of significant importance in certain parts of the Middle Danube Region, to climate change by preserving and improving biodiversity, and widely disseminating these procedures among agricultural experts in the region.

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

Overall, participants of workshops provided valuable, practice-based suggestions both for the development of the dashboard and for design of pilot actions. These are summarized in the subchapters above.

5. Annexes

PP06 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: Workshop on the Climate_CRICES project - Climate_CRICES dashboard

Region/Country: Zagreb, Croatia

Date & location: 27.10.2025., City of Zagreb

Organising partner: PP06 - REGEA

Participants (institutions + short role description):

- Nikola Petković, Marijo Spajić - GEOS (City Office for Economy, Environmental Sustainability and Strategic Planning), City of Zagreb
- Miljenko Sedlar, Tijana Šimek, Jelena Marković, Juraj Tašler, Karlo Vinković - REGEA

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- Why the workshop was organised.
The workshop was organised as a local capacity-building activity to raise knowledge and engage local authorities in using climate information for spatial planning. Precisely, the workshop was organised to show and demonstrate to the representatives of the City of Zagreb the newer version of the Climate_CRICES dashboard, especially in the terms of data visualization and policy measures which can be beneficial and ready-to-use not only for the strategic planning, but also for presentation to the public in informative terms, and also for improving the existing SECAP document in a form of an addendum. The workshop was also organized to collect feedback regarding the newer version of the dashboard, on its functionality, friendly-usage and possible disadvantages/room for improvement.
- How it connects to Climate_CRICES.
The main connection is the stakeholder engagement in the terms of understanding the dashboard functionality as a form of a tool for conducting better and higher quality adaptation plans and programs, with the final goal of reaching a higher level of climate resilience of the region through implementing better adaptation measures.
- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.
Stakeholder feedback collected during the final discussion and Q&A will be communicated to dashboard developers and used to refine usability and functionality. The workshop also helped identify priority climate risks and

practical needs (e.g., better navigation, more hands-on time), which will inform the design of Pilot Actions and follow-up capacity-building sessions.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Time: 10:00 - 12:00

- 10:00 - 10:15
 - Introduction: Project overview, glossary and data sources
General introduction to the project and its context, key climate terminology and data used in the dashboard.
- 10:15 - 10:30
 - Dashboard introduction
A brief overview of what is available on the dashboard.
- 10:30 - 11:00
 - Dashboard in practice
Detailed walkthrough of the dashboard aimed at improving user familiarity and showcasing its advantages - fast access to key information supporting quicker and more informed decision-making.
- 11:00 - 12:00
 - Detailed discussion including Q&A and stakeholder feedback to be communicated to the dashboard developers.

Materials as annex.

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

1) Heatwaves / Urban Heat Island (UHI) - identified as a major risk for Zagreb, due to increasing number of hot days and heatwaves in combination with high percentage of high-sealed areas and low percentage of green infrastructure in several parts of the City, which leads to higher health risk (especially with vulnerable population), quality of life and energy demand for cooling; dashboard indicators and maps were used to explore heat exposure and related impacts.

2) Flood risk (especially flash floods) - discussed as another significant challenge, due to increased frequency and value of intense rainfall events, in combination with high percentage of high-sealed areas and non-adequate stormwater drainage system; the dashboard was used to support understanding of flood-related indicators relevant for urban planning and preparedness.

3) Biodiversity (loss) - not as much prioritised as it is a “newer theme” and hasn’t been evaluated or analysed enough, especially in the terms of climate change impact on biodiversity. The dashboard could support the understanding of biodiversity-related indicators and applicable measures/strategies to address it.

4.2 Identified Barriers

Data - Limited access to up-to-date and better-resolution datasets or varying data licensing conditions. The lack of geoservers, both regional and national, especially for the topic of climate and climate change data (both statistical and spatial) is quite problematic and won’t be fixed soon.

Indicators - lack of consistency between indicator sets; some indicators are scarce, primarily for biodiversity, and there’s insufficient link between indicators and adaptation objectives (measures to be precise).

Governance - lack of capacity to work with climate-related policies or projects, insufficient knowledge of practical data usage, low motivation and experience; still a long way to completely understand and apply climate change in regular spatial planning and regular governance activities.

4.3 Identified Needs

Regarding the Climate_CRICES dashboard:

Technical - the current version is not sufficiently user-friendly - the navigation could be more intuitive (at this moment it’s seems the dashboard is “jumping” from one section to another without workflow or analysis logic). There should be better import-export options (import wms, export map or an option with WFS server to be compatible with GIS) and a data library.

Organisational - regular updates on datasets and indicators, stronger integration of the dashboard into formal planning processes.

Practical - Improved communication between technical experts and decision-makers; more time for hands-on exercises in future sessions and access to an updated, more user-friendly dashboard version.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

(Shared datasets, synergies, potential working groups etc)

- Continue and deepen cooperation between GEOS and REGEA around shared workflows for climate-informed planning.
- Establish a structured feedback loop with dashboard developers (e.g., regular check-ins or a small user group) to test and validate updates.
- Explore shared datasets and harmonised indicators to support both local planning and broader regional/national reporting needs.

- Organise follow-up trainings once the updated dashboard version becomes available.
- For Croatia - Cooperation with the Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service (DHMZ) is much needed, although it is unlikely it'll be possible in the near future

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

- Practical use of the Climate_CRICES dashboard for local and regional planning (every spatial type of document/strategy/action plan to which climate and climate change is relevant, especially in the terms of climate adaptation).
- Higher usage of climate data, indicators, measures and policies that are available on the dashboard, and are applicable to the Zagreb region.
- Operational integration of dashboard outputs into SECAP-linked planning and decision processes.

5.2 Processes that need testing

- Translating dashboard indicators into prioritised adaptation measures and investment decisions.
- Using maps/charts to communicate risks and options to decision-makers and stakeholders.
- Iterative co-design: capturing user feedback, updating the tool, and re-testing with end users.

5.3 Limitations to consider

- Current usability constraints of the dashboard may limit wider uptake until improvements are delivered.
- Dataset availability and licensing conditions could affect indicator updates and local tailoring.
- Variable user experience levels may require differentiated training formats and support materials.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

- Pilot workflow for GEOS planners: a standardised 'dashboard-to-decision' process for selecting heat/UHI and flash-flood measures.

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

- Keep combining technical content with interactive practice and facilitated discussion to build confidence.

- Provide more hands-on time and ensure access to the updated, more user-friendly dashboard in future sessions.
- Maintain regular follow-up capacity-building activities to support sustained dashboard use in planning and decision-making.

6. Annexes

- participant list ([LINK](#))
- photo

Radionica na projektu Climate_CRICES Zagreb, 27. listopada 2025.		
POPIS SUDIONIKA		
IME I PREZIME	INSTITUCIJA	POTPIS
MILJENKO SEDLAR	REGEA	
JELENA MARKOVIĆ	REGEA	
TIJANA ŠIMEK	REGEA	
MARJO SPAJIC	ZAGREB	
NIKOLA PETKOVIĆ	GEOS	
KARLO VINKOVIĆ	REGEA	
JURAJ TAŠER	REGEA	

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PP07 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: Cross-border knowledge base for climate impact adaptation - INTERREG project Climate_CRICES (IOER).

Region/Country: Saxony/Germany

Date & location: Online, 26 February 2026

Organising partner: IOER through LfULG

Participants (institutions + short role description):

A total of 11 participants representing a mix of federal-national (e.g. Kompetenzzentrum Klima), regional-sectoral (e.g. SMUL or LfULG), and municipal actors (City of Leipzig, Sächsische Schweiz-Osterzgebirge, Zittau, etc.).

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

The workshop was organised to support municipal staff in better understanding and effectively using the Climate_CRICES dashboard as a practical tool for climate adaptation planning and decision-making. It aimed to strengthen participants' capacity to interpret climate-related data, compare regional strategies, and integrate evidence-based insights into their daily work. The workshop is directly linked to the objectives of Climate_CRICES, which seeks to enhance the ability of public authorities to respond to climate risks through improved access to data, tools, and governance-oriented guidance. By familiarising local practitioners with the dashboard and its underlying logic, the workshop contributes to building the institutional competences promoted by the project. The feedback, experiences, and needs identified during the workshop will be systematically analysed and used to refine the Pilot Action planning process, ensuring that proposed measures are grounded in practical realities, aligned with local capacities, and responsive to the priorities of municipal administrations.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Timeline	Session	Content	Format & Tools
11:00 – 11:05	Welcome and getting acquainted	Introduction of participants, overview of objectives	Free talking and presentation
11:05 – 11:15	Introduction to Climate_CRICES	Overview of project aims, focus areas (heat & drought, flooding, biodiversity),	Short presentation
11:15 – 11:45	Presentation of the dashboard	Presentation of the Climate_CRICES dashboard, its main features and how it could be used for municipalities; Time for Q&A by participants	Presentation & Q&A
11:45 – 12:00	Closing	Final words of thanks and short feedback from participants	Menti and host closing remarks

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

Heat& Drought, followed by heavy precipitation and flooding, and biodiversity.

4.2 Identified Barriers

- **Financial constraints and high costs:** Lack of accessible funding, strained municipal budgets, high investment and maintenance costs, and local structural constraints.
- **Limited human resources:** Insufficient staff capacities and an increasing number of responsibilities for municipalities.

- **Lack of legal enforceability:** Absence of clear, legally binding requirements and obligations for climate adaptation.
- **Knowledge and awareness gaps:** Limited understanding of climate issues and insufficient sensitivity to climate relevance among decision-makers and politicians.
- **Political inertia and uncertainty:** Low political will, uncertainty about cost-benefit relations, and a focus on short-term measures that may cause long-term harm.

4.3 Identified Needs

- **Improved data, evidence, and early-stage planning support:** Accessible, high-quality data; tools for site-specific analysis; sufficient time and structured support in early (“phase zero”) planning, including pilot and demonstration projects.
- **Reliable and adequate financing mechanisms:** Binding, long-term funding for personnel and measures; financial support for implementation (not only concepts); and funding schemes that avoid the need for municipal pre-financing.
- **Strengthened capacities and skills:** Availability of qualified staff; continuous training and upskilling; and interdisciplinary expertise across water management, green infrastructure, heat-adapted building, and climate-resilient infrastructure.
- **Enhanced governance and coordination across levels:** Stronger cross-departmental and cross-level cooperation (federal, state, municipal); integrated planning; and systematic combination of grey infrastructure with nature-based solutions.
- **Active engagement and societal buy-in:** Targeted support to “meet municipalities where they are”; early and continuous involvement of local populations; and wider dissemination of successful projects supported by transparent facts and cost-benefit analyses.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

- **Harmonised principles and data sharing:** Joint standards, simplified and interoperable data exchange, and shared information platforms to support coordinated climate adaptation planning.
- **Cross-border and regional strategies:** Co-development of transboundary and regional climate adaptation strategies, including joint measures through river basin and transboundary waters commissions, and mutual learning via city partnerships.
- **Institutional cooperation in border regions (Euroregions):** Strengthening structured collaboration between local and regional authorities in border regions to jointly address climate risks while fostering economic and cultural development.
- **Coordination and contact infrastructures:** Creation of shared contact lists and databases identifying focal points by theme and responsibility, improving transparency on who is responsible for what across institutions and regions.
- **EU-funded cooperation frameworks (e.g. INTERREG):** Leveraging EU programmes to finance and scale cooperation projects that overcome physical borders,

administrative fragmentation, and differing legal frameworks in climate adaptation.

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

The next phase should prioritise *enabling* conditions for climate adaptation. Realistic actions from the requested ones voiced by the stakeholders include consolidating and curating accessible, practice-oriented data packages and decision-support tools focused on heat, drought, flooding, and biodiversity; developing concise guidance for early-stage (“phase zero”) planning that helps municipalities scope options without committing funding; and producing a small set of evidence-based case briefs (including cost-benefit narratives) drawn from existing projects. The project can also strengthen capacities through targeted peer-learning formats (workshops, clinics, community-of-practice exchanges) and by setting up a lightweight cooperation infrastructure (contact overviews, thematic mappings, shared repositories) to facilitate cross-municipal and cross-border learning. Finally, focused communication and translation activities—summarising key insights in accessible language and formats—can raise awareness and usability of results among municipal practitioners without requiring formal policy change.

5.2 Usefulness and usability of the tool

A short menti survey indicates that the dashboard is perceived as most valuable as a **justification and communication tool**, particularly for explaining and defending climate adaptation measures to superiors, politicians, or the public (highest score). It also provides **clear added professional value**, generating new insights that support the further development of municipal climate adaptation strategies. Respondents find the dashboard moderately helpful for **understanding local climate risks** and for **informing decision-making**, suggesting it works well as an analytical support tool. However, the lowest score relates to **integration into daily administrative work**, indicating that while the dashboard is strategically useful, its operational usability in routine planning, reporting, and coordination could be further strengthened.

The survey further shows that the dashboard is generally perceived as **clear, well structured, and easy to navigate**, with particularly high scores for the **logic and usability of filters and selection options** as well as the ability to **quickly find relevant information**. Visual presentations such as maps, tables, and graphics are also rated positively, supporting comprehension. However, respondents feel **less confident in continuing to use the dashboard independently after the workshop**, indicating a need for additional guidance, onboarding materials, or light-touch support to strengthen user autonomy despite the otherwise strong usability performance.

5.3 Limitations to consider

A key limitation of the findings relates to the composition of the invited audience, which consisted primarily of municipal climate change adaptation managers or units responsible for mitigation and adaptation within municipalities. While highly relevant as **end users**, this group may not be the primary actors responsible for *designing* climate adaptation strategies, a task that is often outsourced to engineering and consulting firms commissioned by cities and municipalities. This raises questions about whether the tool was assessed by the most appropriate target group. In addition, participants highlighted a sense of being already overwhelmed by the extensive volume of existing guidance and tools available in Germany, leading to critical reflections on **the need for additional information**. In this context, the added value of incorporating non-German data, approaches, or examples was questioned, particularly regarding how such international content complements or goes beyond established national guidance and supports concrete local decision-making.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

- **Reduce language barriers:** Systematically provide translations of key materials, tools, and guidance to ensure accessibility across regions, sectors, and user groups.
- **Increase visibility and awareness:** Actively disseminate information on available tools, initiatives, and good practices to address the issue of solutions “not yet being known.”
- **Establish a community of users:** Build and support a user community for exchange, peer learning, and feedback, enabling continuous improvement and wider uptake of climate adaptation approaches.

6. Annexes

- participant list (GDPR!)

Teilnehmer (11)

Eine Stunde fürs Klima | Sprechstunde vom Fachzentrum Klima im Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und G... Meeting-Info 43:38

Dominic Rumpf - LfULG Nicht verifiziert		Jan J. SD Nicht verifiziert	C.Härtling LDS Nicht verifiziert	Ralf Koppitz LPV SOE Nicht verifiziert
Dolmetscherin Romy P. Nicht verifiziert	Oliver Gebhardt (Kompeten... Nicht verifiziert	Manja Neubert, SMUL Sach... Nicht verifiziert	Brüggemann, KAM Leipzig Nicht verifiziert	Frank Uebel Nicht verifiziert
Henker, Jana autobahn.de	B. Jahn Nicht verifiziert	Sommer Nicht verifiziert		

Anzeigen des freigegebenen Inhalts von IOR

Risk of losses in crop production due to extreme precipitation

Region	Mean precipitation events (per year)
1	8
2	12
3	44

Indicators

- Jens
Nicht verifiziert
- Dolmetscherin Romy P.
Nicht verifiziert
- C.Härtling LDS
Nicht verifiziert
- Brüggemann, KAM Leip...
Nicht verifiziert
- Jens
Nicht verifiziert
- Manja Neubert, SMUL S...
Nicht verifiziert
- Gerard Hutter
Nicht verifiziert
- Sommer
Nicht verifiziert
- Dominic Rumpf - LfULG
Nicht verifiziert
- Henker, Jana
Extern
- Oliver Gebhardt (Kompe...
Nicht verifiziert
- C.Härtling LDS
Nicht verifiziert
- Dolmetscherin Romy P.
Nicht verifiziert
- B. Jahn
Nicht verifiziert

- Jan J. SD
ⓘ Nicht verifiziert
- Jens
ⓘ Nicht verifiziert
- Ralf Koppitz LPV SOE
ⓘ Nicht verifiziert
- Frank Uebel
ⓘ Nicht verifiziert

- photos/screenshots

PP08 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: From Data to Decisions. Practical Adaptation Planning: Lower and Cross-Border Areas

Region/Country: Dolnośląskie Voivodeship, Poland

Date & location: 27.02.2026, online

Organising partner: UPWr

Participants (institutions + short role description):

Local authorities: City of Warsaw Office, City of Kraków Office, City of Jelenia Góra Office, City of Opole Office, Marshal's Office of the Podkarpackie Voivodeship

- Provide practical insights into local adaptation needs and priorities.
- Share experience from urban planning and climate policy implementation.
- Help validate the tool's applicability in real administrative contexts.

State / Research Institutions: Institute for Territorial Development, Polish Waters, The Main School of Fire Service, Lower Silesian Agricultural Advisory Centre in Wrocław, Institute of Environmental Protection – National Research Institute, Institute of Urban and Regional Development, Karkonosze Regional Development Agency S.A., Śnieżka Forest District, Regional Directorate of State Forests in Wrocław, Wrocław Centre for Technology Transfer, Wrocław University of Science and Technology

- Scientific knowledge, data, and methodological expertise.
- Advise on relevant indicators and metrics for climate adaptation planning.
- Support technical validation of the tool and its analytical outputs.

Private sector: FPP Enviro, Sweco Poland, EKOLOG, Projectiff Ltd., Greater Poland Academy of Science and Development

- Provide technical expertise and practical solutions for implementation.
- Offer feedback on usability, feasibility, and integration of the tool in operational contexts.
- Help identify innovative approaches to support local adaptation planning.

NGOs: Natura Polska Foundation, Landscape Protection Foundation, SE ETNA

- Represent community interests and environmental priorities.
- Contribute knowledge of local ecosystems, conservation, and sustainable practices.
- Ensure that social and ecological dimensions are considered in adaptation planning.

Active participant profile (Menti): most respondents represented local government/administration and research/advisory institutions; responses covered multiple Polish locations (not only Dolnośląskie).

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- The purpose of the meeting.

The purpose of the meeting was to present and demonstrate the tool (dashboard) being developed within the Climate_CRICES project, which is designed to support local governments in planning and implementing climate change adaptation measures. The workshop aims to engage stakeholders from local authorities, research institutions, the private sector, and NGOs, allowing them to provide feedback on the tool's functionality, usability, and relevance to regional needs.

In addition, the meeting seeks to identify data and indicator requirements, discuss regional risks and priorities, and gather insights that will help refine the tool and guide the planning of Pilot Actions within the project. How it connects to Climate_CRICES.

The workshop is directly linked to the Climate_CRICES project, as it focuses on presenting and testing the tool (dashboard) being developed within the project. This tool is designed to support local governments in planning climate change adaptation by providing access to relevant data, indicators, and analyses. The workshop also gathers input from key stakeholders – including local authorities, state and research institutions, the private sector, and NGOs – which helps ensure that the tool meets the practical needs of users in real-world conditions.

- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning.

The insights and feedback collected during the workshop – regarding data needs, indicators, regional risks, and priorities – will be used to inform the design and implementation of Pilot Actions within the Climate_CRICES project. This includes adjusting the tool to local conditions, identifying key areas of intervention, and ensuring that the proposed adaptation measures are relevant, actionable, and aligned with stakeholder expectations. In this way, the workshop serves as a bridge between tool development and practical, on-the-ground Pilot Actions.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Workshop agenda:

- Presentation of the project and the tool supporting local adaptation,
- Summary of activities carried out to date,
- Lower Silesian Water Policy (presentation by IRT)
- Risks and priorities for the region,
- Discussion on participants' needs regarding data and indicators,
- Summary: recommendations and next steps.

Format: online

Tools: Google Meet, Miro, Menti

The host presented the current state of the Climate_CRICES work and the emerging dashboard and framed the workshop as feedback collection for the tool and addenda supporting adaptation planning.

IRT presented the Lower Silesian Water Policy context, including the retention potential analysis approach (geoportal spatial base, reports for municipalities and catchments), typologies of retention, land-use conflicts, and the point that there is no fully unified retention assessment method.

The organisers presented the dashboard concept and planned functionalities (filters, comparisons, export), and described a baseline approach prioritising open-licence sources (with Copernicus C3S mentioned as preferred baseline), with higher-resolution options potentially constrained by licensing/commercial access.

The organisers explained the workshop flow and tools (Menti for voting and questions, Miro for structured feedback on tool functionality and database content).

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

Stakeholders most frequently associated local adaptation planning with risks such as flooding/local inundations and heavy rainfall, drought/water scarcity, and heat/heat waves (incl. UHI-related framing in responses).

Related topics raised in the discussion included water retention planning and risk-aware spatial planning.

Fig.1. Interests of the 46 participants who registered for the workshop

4.2 Identified Barriers

Data and indicator barriers

Stakeholders indicated that data is missing most strongly for:

1. monitoring effects (impact tracking),
2. risk identification,
investment justification,
3. action planning and reporting (also rated as significant gaps).

Participants signalled that not only availability but also interpretability matters: they need definitions, simple explanations, and sources clearly attached to indicators.

A practical constraint raised in the notes is format friction: SHP is recognised as outdated but still the most “real-life” format people ask for and expect to handle without specialised workflows, so extraction/testing of such formats was explicitly mentioned.

Usability barriers: interface readability and language accessibility (need for clearer explanations and translations).

4.3 Identified Needs

What users want most in the dashboard: spatial data layers and location-specific information, plus ready-made indicators usable directly at municipal scale.

- Strong preference for an explicit “interpretation layer”: guidance that explains what a given indicator means, how it should (and should not) be used, and what the limitations are.
- Ready-to-use indicators for municipalities (pre-calculated values) plus clear interpretation guidance.
- Participants asked for export and reporting-friendly functionality, not just visual browsing.
- A consistent thread in the notes is: curated data library with metadata and practical support (including calculators and short instructions), rather than simply adding more raw datasets.
- Training/support materials (plain-language definitions, examples, and short how-to instructions).

Stakeholder questions recorded in the notes include:

- need for clear indicator definitions and non-technical explanations plus sources,
- where data is missing most and what should be prioritised,
- what is most useful: ready indicators for municipalities vs other functions,
- whether the tool can be extended/replicated to other regions in Poland,
- whether social/health data on vulnerable populations can be included for communication and decision support.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

- Participants expressed interest in sharing datasets and documents in a structured format so they can be integrated into the regional dashboard content during piloting.
- Sharing good practices and project outputs that often get lost after projects end, via the dashboard repository.
- There was also a question about whether expanding the tool to other Polish regions is possible, which will be discussed in follow-up

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

The workshop confirms that the pilot analytical scope should keep the three thematic areas central (heat and drought, flooding/heavy rainfall, biodiversity impacts), but with a strong emphasis on drought/water scarcity, flooding/local inundations and heat waves as the most “actionable” and repeatedly mentioned local priorities:

- Flooding and heavy rainfall impacts (incl. local inundations and flash floods).
- Drought and water scarcity (incl. groundwater decline) and related retention solutions.
- Heat stress and urban heat island effects in built-up areas.

5.2 Processes that need testing

- Prioritise pilot workflows that directly address the strongest stakeholder data gaps: monitoring effects, risk identification, investment justification, and reporting outputs.
- Treat “interpretation layer” as a deliverable, not a nice-to-have: indicator definitions, plain language explanation, sources, and “how to use / limitations”.
- Interpretation support: piloting how to provide indicator definitions, plain-language explanations and “how to use / how not to use” guidance to avoid misinterpretation and support credible decisions.
- Data access practicality: testing the “baseline first” approach (open/licence-friendly sources as default, with optional higher resolution where feasible) and providing short instructions for datasets requiring accounts or coding.
- Consider a pilot extension test case or at least a documented pathway for replication to other PL regions (because this was explicitly asked).

5.3 Limitations to consider

- Menti results represent responses from those who answered, not the whole attendance (the export notes indicate partial response)

- Data gaps are most acute for monitoring effects, so early pilot outputs should be explicit about what can and cannot be evaluated.
- Some needs relate to usability and communication, not only data coverage (readability and clarity of the interface were explicitly raised).
- Stakeholder capacity varies; the tool needs different entry levels (basic views vs advanced analysis).
- Definitions and administrative vs catchment boundaries differ; this needs transparent communication in the dashboard.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

- Test a small set of municipality-level 'core indicators' (spatial + time series) with interpretation notes and report export.
- Use DPW retention potential layers as a case study for integrating local spatial datasets into the dashboard workflow.

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

- Prioritise usability: clear visual hierarchy, translation, and plain-language explanations alongside technical metadata.
- Focus on a curated indicator set and data library; avoid overloading the dashboard with disconnected datasets.
- add a clear interpretation layer (definitions, sources, limitations) to keep the tool usable for non-experts and credible for experts.

6. Annexes

- Photos

- Screenshots

Climate crices (Presenting)

Założenia projektu Climate CRICES

- HEAT & DROUGHT**
 - Effects include:
 - Agricultural decline
 - Water stress
 - Public health risks
- FLOODING**
 - Effects include:
 - damage to infrastructure
 - disrupted mobility
 - soil erosion
- BIODIVERSITY LOSS**
 - Effects include:
 - Species decline
 - Habitat fragmentation
 - Invasive species

Brak spójnych danych utrudnia planowanie i porównania między krajami

Regiony potrzebują narzędzi do prognoz i decyzji, by planować skutecznie adaptację do zmiany klimatu

Climate_CRICES tworzy wspólny dashboard danych klimatycznych

- wsparcie władz regionalnych w działaniach adaptacyjnych przy użyciu narzędzia opartego na danych (dashboardu).

• Menti results

📍 Twoja miejscowość lub obszar zainteresowania

👤 10 / 19

Jaką instytucję reprezentujesz?

Jakie wyzwanie klimatyczne jest dziś najważniejsze dla Twojej miejscowości/organizacji?

Najbardziej przydatne w Dashboardzie byłyby:

Kilka pytań na koniec

Na ile ta krótka sesja była dla Ciebie przydatna?

Na ile przedstawione narzędzie jest dla Ciebie czytelne

CC Dashboard będzie przydatny w mojej pracy

0

5

Q&A

3 3

All questions

Answered

Unanswered

Sort by Most upvotes

- Czy zastosowane wskaźniki mają swoje definicje (są jasno wyjaśnione językiem nie specjalistycznym), i wskazane są ich źródła?

0

- Czy wskaźniki uwzględniają wskaźniki wymagane przy opracowaniu do MPA (jeszcze nie ma Rozporządzenia, ale MKiŚ opublikował ich aktualizację po konsultacjach) czy brałście Państwo je pod uwagę?

0

- Jakie macie Państwo macie rekomendacje do osób po raz pierwszy wykonujących plan zagospodarowania wód opadowych i roztopowych dla wybranej gminy? Jak w tym kontekście skorzystać z Państwa wyników?

0

PP09 Workshop report

Workshop Report

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: 2nd CZ WORKSHOP / PRE-TRAINING MEETING

Region/Country: Liberec region, Czechia

Date & location: November 10, 2025, online (Zoom)

Organising partner: PP09 - UJEP

Participants (institutions + short role description):

- Pavel Farský - Hrádek and Nisou municipality
- Leona Patočková, Kryštof Tichý - Regional Development Agency (ARR)
- Václav Židek - Jablonec nad Nisou city (Department of Spatial and Strategic Planning)
- Marek Nevečeřal - Liberec region (environmental office)
- Jan Macháč, Štěpánka Truhlářová, Lenka Zaňková - UJEP

2. Workshop Context and Objectives

- Why the workshop was organised
 - The second Czech stakeholder workshop in the Liberec Region was organised to present the ongoing results of the Interreg CE project Climate_CRICES and to engage key regional and local stakeholders in a discussion on data use for climate change adaptation. In particular, the workshop introduced the emerging Climate_CRICES dashboard and summarised the analysis of available data sources, adaptation strategies and plans, with the aim of collecting feedback on data needs, usability of the tool and options for its practical application in local and regional adaptation planning. Another aim was to initiate a discussion on the possible addendum and topics for future training webinars.
- How it connects to Climate_CRICES
 - The workshop was part of the stakeholder engagement process foreseen within Climate_CRICES Activity 2.1. It served to explain the project progress and main outputs (the Climate_CRICES strategy, the data platform Dashboard), and to discuss local addenda to adaptation plans. Main aim was to demonstrate how the dashboard links climate data, impact indicators and information from adaptation documents across all pilot regions and territories, and how can our stakeholders use the dashboard. Special attention was given to the Liberec Region and the Nisa river basin, including possibilities for cross-border data sharing and for using the dashboard as a gateway to relevant datasets, indicators and supporting materials for adaptation. A demo dashboard video was shown.

- How its results will feed into Pilot Action planning
 - Inputs from participants will directly inform the design of the Czech pilot actions. Stakeholders identified potential uses of the dashboard for revising the climate risk and vulnerability assessment and proposed measures in the adaptation strategy of Hrádek nad Nisou, for updating objectives in line with new legislative requirements, and for creating a data library and simple algorithms that could be integrated into the Liberec Region portal and used by municipalities such as Jablonec nad Nisou. They also suggested topics and target groups for future webinars on adaptation, data use and communication of measures, which will be taken into account when planning pilot activities focused on practical application of the dashboard and capacity building in the region.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Workshop Programme

1) Introduction

Presentation of the project progress and its main objectives

Brief introduction to the adaptation strategy

2) Climate_CRICES Dashboard version 2 (approx. 15 min)

Overview of the dashboard logic and flow

Walk-through of the three main elements (video + own demonstration)

- policies and strategies and their comparison across regions
- general guidance on how to develop climate change adaptation strategies
- step-by-step information and data for identifying and interpreting climate risks, adaptation measures, and monitoring and evaluation of adaptation effects

3) Discussion on the Dashboard

Eliciting feedback on use, usability and usefulness of the dashboard (using 7 pre-prepared questions)

4) Practical Use of the Dashboard

Our perspective on how to use and test the dashboard in practice

Short case studies linked to selected participants and how specific parts of the dashboard could support their work

5) Follow-up Activities

Presentation of the plan for four coaching webinars and opportunities for participants to get involved

Invitation for Tri-border workshop

Pilot action and addendum discussion

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

(ranking and short explanation)

Flooding and heavy rainfall (highest priority): Increased frequency of intense rainfall events and flash floods, especially in the Nisa river basin and in urban areas, is seen as a key climate risk. It can overload drainage systems, increase flood hazard for settlements and infrastructure, and worsen water quality.

Heatwaves, droughts and rising temperatures: Growing number of hot days and heatwaves affects human health, quality of life in cities and energy demand. Urban areas in the Liberec Region are particularly vulnerable due to heat island effects and limited green infrastructure in some locations. Periods of low precipitation and higher evapotranspiration lead to drought stress for ecosystems, agriculture and forestry, and can reduce water availability for households and industry, which is relevant for the Nisa river basin.

Impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity: Changes in temperature and precipitation patterns, together with extreme events, put additional pressure on forests, rivers and protected areas. Stakeholders noted that biodiversity aspects are still insufficiently reflected in adaptation planning.

4.2 Identified Barriers

(Data, Indicators, Governance)

Data - fragmented datasets across institutions, limited practical use in strategies and lack of clear metadata on sources and periods.

Indicators - inconsistent indicator sets between regions and countries, gaps for some risks (e.g. biodiversity), weak links between indicators and adaptation objectives, too many different options, zero overlap into practical use.

Governance - low staff capacity to work with data (time/motivation/experiences), reliance on projects for tool development and maintenance, and insufficient alignment between legal requirements and available data/tools.

4.3 Identified Needs

(Technical, Organisational, Practical)

Key needs for better use of the Climate_CRICES dashboard and data were:

General - participants found it difficult to evaluate the dashboard in its current (demo) form. Once real data are available, they will be able to comment on the dashboard's actual potential.

Technical - easy regional/municipal comparison (e.g. heat maps), export and import functions, API access, a data library with simple calculators and clear metadata in multiple languages.

Organisational - agreed responsibilities for data management, regular updates of datasets and indicators, content adapted to the new directives, and stronger integration of the dashboard into formal planning processes.

Practical/capacity-building - focused webinars and trainings on working with data and the dashboard within real world scenarios, guidance on revising risk and vulnerability assessments, support for communication of benefits of adaptation measures to residents.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

(Shared datasets, synergies, potential working groups etc.)

Opportunities for cooperation are mainly linked to data management. The Regional Development Agency (ARR) expressed its willingness to participate in the possible updating of datasets used in the Climate_CRICES dashboard and pointed out that the data viewed in the dashboard can be downloaded. This creates a basis for shared use and regular updating of these datasets in support of regional and local planning. The city of Jablonec found it useful to receive the algorithms for data processing so they could implement the datasets into their own systems.

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

Practical use of the Climate_CRICES dashboard for regional and local adaptation planning in the Liberec Region and the Nisa river basin.

Better use of climate and impact data and indicators, including those currently underused in strategies (e.g. biodiversity-related aspects).

Support for local adaptation addenda by demonstrating how dashboard data can feed into existing adaptation strategies and plans.

Sharing information on how different countries are **implementing new directives** (e.g. wastewater treatment regulations) including technologies used, legislative approaches, and practical progress across regions.

5.2 Processes that need testing

The workshop pointed to several processes that would benefit from pilot testing:

Downloading and reusing dashboard datasets in practice (export functions, use of the data library).

Cooperation between UJEP, ARR and municipalities on updating and maintaining datasets used in the dashboard.

Using the dashboard as a basis for targeted follow-up meetings with individual institutions to tailor data and outputs to their needs.

Organising online webinars as a tool for awareness-raising and effective capacity building.

5.3 Limitations to consider

Pilot actions need to take into account:

No systematic update of some datasets within the project (e.g. adaptation strategies), even though stakeholders are interested in updates.

Limited functionality regarding sharing of documents and literature directly via the dashboard.

Time and capacity constraints of municipal and regional staff and the fact that non-accredited events may be less attractive for some target groups.

Lower motivation and interest of stakeholders in the Dashboard usage than expected.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

Based on the discussion, potential pilot actions could include:

A dashboard testing pilot with ARR and selected municipalities (e.g. Jablonec nad Nisou), focusing on downloading and using data for concrete analytical tasks and real adaptation planning.

A data update pilot where ARR and UJEP jointly test procedures for updating and documenting selected datasets used in the dashboard.

A small webinar series on climate change, adaptation tools (including the dashboard) and practical topics such as wastewater treatment, building on the expressed interests of regional stakeholders.

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

From the workshop, the main lessons for pilot action design are:

Keep pilot actions closely linked to real tasks of regional and local institutions so that the use of the dashboard is clearly practical.

Involve key stakeholders early (ARR, municipalities, region) through individual online meetings to co-shape pilot activities.

Prioritise features that stakeholders explicitly asked for (data export, clear metadata, language versions) when designing pilots.

When planning webinars, consider cooperation with existing training/accreditation schemes or other incentives to make participation easier and more attractive.

Effective discussion of the dashboard requires more interactive discussion methods and using real data + allowing stakeholders to explore the dashboard themselves.

6. Annexes

- Screenshots + participants list

zoom Workplace Meeting Stěpánka Truhlářová's screen

Participants: Jan Machac, Stěpánka Truhlářová, Václav Židek, Kryštof, Leona Patočková, Pavel Farský

Progres projektu Climate_CRICES

DASHBOARD WORKSHOP

interreg CENTRAL EUROPE Co-funded by the European Union

Climate_CRICES

Online Workshop

Jan Macháč
Stěpánka Truhlářová
Lenka Zaňková

Audio Video Participants 6 Chat React Share Host tools AI Companion Meeting info Apps Record More End

zoom Workplace Meeting Stěpánka Truhlářová's screen

Participants: Jan Machac, Stěpánka Truhlářová, Václav Židek, Marek Neveceřal

SHRNUTÍ VÝSLEDKŮ ANALÝZ ADAPTAČNÍCH STRATEGIÍ A DAT

RELEVANTNÍ INDIKÁTORY

HORKO A SUCHO

- Horké dny
- Dny vln veder
- Tropické noci
- Počet po sobě jdoucích suchých dnů
- Průměrná teplota

POVODNĚ

- Maximální 5denní úhrn srážek
- Maximální denní průtok
- Počet dnů se srážkami ≥ 30 mm/den
- Celkový roční úhrn srážek
- Ztráty na infrastruktuře a životech
- Změna využití půdy

DOPADY NA BIODIVERZITU

- Index běžných druhů ptáků
- Počet mrazivých dní
- Počet dní s vysokým rizikem požárů
- Ekologický status vod

PILOTNÍ REGIONY

Region	Horko a sucho	Povodně	Biodiverzita
IT	★	★	★
ES	★	★	★
FR	★	★	★
PL	★	★	★
DE	★	★	★
CZ	★	★	★
SK	★	★	★
HU	★	★	★
RO	★	★	★
BG	★	★	★
GR	★	★	★
PT	★	★	★
IE	★	★	★
UK	★	★	★
SI	★	★	★
EL	★	★	★
MT	★	★	★
LU	★	★	★
BE	★	★	★
NL	★	★	★
DK	★	★	★
SE	★	★	★
NO	★	★	★
FI	★	★	★
IS	★	★	★
CH	★	★	★
AT	★	★	★
UA	★	★	★
PL	★	★	★
CZ	★	★	★
SK	★	★	★
HU	★	★	★
RO	★	★	★
BG	★	★	★
GR	★	★	★
PT	★	★	★
IE	★	★	★
UK	★	★	★
SI	★	★	★
EL	★	★	★
MT	★	★	★
LU	★	★	★
BE	★	★	★
NL	★	★	★
DK	★	★	★
SE	★	★	★
NO	★	★	★
FI	★	★	★
IS	★	★	★
CH	★	★	★
AT	★	★	★
UA	★	★	★

LEGENDA

- indikátor ve strategii i datech
- datová mezera
- ★ nevyužitý potenciál dat
- chybí data i zmínka

Indikátor změn ve strategii	Dostupná data
ano	ano
ne	ne
ne	ano
ne	ne

Participants (7)

- Jan Machac (Host, me)
- Stěpánka Truhlářová
- Marek Neveceřal
- Kryštof
- Leona Patočková
- Pavel Farský
- Václav Židek

NEW New co-host abilities!
They cannot only control the meeting but also manage meeting assets after the meeting!

Invite Mute all

PP07+PP08+PP09 Workshop report

Workshop Report

Executive Summary - Tri-Border Climate Adaptation Workshop

The tri-border workshop brought together institutions from Poland, Czechia, and Germany to strengthen cross-border cooperation on climate data, monitoring, and adaptation planning within the Neisse catchment. The event was held within the Climate_CRICES project, which focuses on developing a joint adaptation strategy, a climate data dashboard, and support tools for local adaptation planning.

Participants presented several ongoing climate-related projects in the region, including Wildfire CE, Fragiles Erbe, Twin-Waters, CICADA4CE, and the LIFE project for Liberec Region. These initiatives collectively address wildfire risk, cultural heritage protection, water quality monitoring, digitalization of hydrological systems, and community-based adaptation.

Breakout discussions highlighted major **challenges** in cross-border work: inconsistent data granularity, differing calculation methods, gaps in small catchments, lack of harmonized biodiversity indicators, and varying national legislation. Municipalities face capacity constraints, limited expertise, and financial barriers, making adaptation efforts difficult to implement without external support.

Key **opportunities** for collaboration include development of shared datasets, exchange of hands-on experience, harmonized monitoring systems, and better coordination between national and local levels. Participants expressed strong interest in practical examples of effective measures and support for implementing nature-based solutions.

Menti polling showed that the risks identified in the Climate_CRICES project (**heat and drought, flooding, and biodiversity loss**) fully align with the risks perceived as relevant by the workshop participants. The workshop confirmed the region's commitment to joint climate adaptation, emphasizing the need for harmonized data, integrated platforms, and continued project-to-project linkages to improve resilience in the tri-border area.

1. Basic information and summary

Workshop title: Cross-Border Climate Workshop

Region/Country: Triborder region Poland-Czechia-Germany (Neisse catchment)

Date & location: 20.11.2025, online (Zoom)

Organising partner: PP07 + PP08 + PP09

Participants: 16

- 7 out of 34 invited German-Polish-Czech representatives
- 9 from Climate_CRICES project (organizers)

2. Aim of the workshop

Climate_CRICES hosted a virtual knowledge exchange workshop bringing together research and development projects and programmes that focus on climate change data, information, and knowledge in the German-Polish-Czech tri-border region. The aim was to create a shared space for dialogue, exchange, and collaboration across initiatives that often work in parallel on similar challenges. By connecting these efforts, the workshop helped identify synergies, data gaps, and opportunities for joint action, ultimately supporting municipalities in accessing coherent and complementary climate knowledge for their local adaptation planning. At the same time, it allows projects and donors to better align activities, maximize the impact of existing investments, and strengthen the collective capacity of the region to address the pressing impacts of climate change through coordinated, cross-border solutions.

3. Workshop agenda and structure, format, tools and materials

Agenda:

Time	Session / Activity
9:00 - 9:15	(1) Welcome and Setting the Scene
9:15 - 9:25	(2) Introduction to Climate_CRICES
9:25 - 10:45	(3) Session 1 - Presentations of Projects and Programmes Projects: <i>Wildfire-ce</i> <i>Fragiles Erbe/Kruche dziedzictwo</i> <i>TWIN-Waters</i> <i>CICADA4CE</i> <i>LIFE project - Liberec region</i>
10:45 - 11:00	Break
11:00 - 12:10	(4) Session 2 - Interactive Deliberation: Exploring Synergies
12:10 - 12:25	(5) Wrap-Up and Next Steps
12:25 - 12:30	Closing

Workshop format:

Presentations + interactive deliberation (breakout sessions, whiteboard, Mentimeter)

3.1 Welcome and scene setting

The workshop started off with a welcome and a short tour de table to get to know the participants, as well as their main expertise in the three Climate_CRICES priorities.

The following **institutions** were present:

- Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences (UPWr)
- Polish Ministry of Climate and Environment
- CZ Ministry of Environment
- International Commission on the Protection of the Oder against Pollution
- TU Dresden
- Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)
- Jan Evangelista Purkyně University (UJEP)

Climate-change issues relevant for collaboration:

1. Heat and drought - 6 votes
2. Flooding - 5 votes
3. Biodiversity loss - 4 votes

Prioritization clearly points to **extreme heat and drought** as top shared concern in the tri-border region (fig 1).

Which of these climate-change topics are relevant to you for collaboration?

Fig. 1. Results of a poll concerning relevant topics

3.2 Introduction to Climate_CRICES

Dr. Uciechowska-Grakowicz gave an introduction to the Climate_CRICES project, its aims, current status and next steps. Find the presentation [here](#).

The *Climate_CRICES* project (2024-2026), funded by the Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE Programme, strengthens the capacity of regional and local authorities across Austria, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Czech Republic, Croatia, and Italy to plan and implement effective climate change adaptation measures. Focusing on key climate impacts—heat and drought, flooding and water scarcity, and biodiversity loss—the project brings together existing environmental and climate data from multiple sources and countries. Its main outcome, a multilingual and user-friendly dashboard, helps administrations access, compare, and apply relevant information, strategies, and indicators to improve adaptation planning. By fostering cross-border cooperation and knowledge exchange, Climate_CRICES contributes to building climate resilience and offers a model for integrated adaptation management across Central Europe.

In the transboundary **Neisse catchment**, which spans **Poland, Germany, and the Czech Republic**, *Climate_CRICES* aims to strengthen cross-border cooperation and enhance the capacity of regional and water management authorities to plan for and adapt to climate change. Building on existing frameworks such as the **EU Water Framework Directive** and the **Odra River Basin Management Plan**, the project addresses key regional challenges—**heat and drought, water shortage and flooding, and biodiversity impacts**—by harmonizing and visualizing relevant data across borders. Through **local and transboundary working groups**, the project supports authorities in developing data-based addenda for their regional climate adaptation plans and fosters collaboration among stakeholders to improve projections, information use, and adaptive measures for sustainable water management in the Neisse region.

Main project outputs:

- Joint strategy for improving climate change adaptation planning
- Climate data dashboard
- Strengthening the integration of climate information into decision-making

3.3 Presentation of Projects and Programmes

Project (link)	Description	Synergies with Climate_CRICES	Presentation during Triborder workshop
Wildfire-ce	Vegetation fires in Central Europe	Data sources	<p>Focus: vegetation fires in Central Europe and their increase towards 2080 (prediction - modelling)</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved and harmonized fire danger maps in border areas; - Identification of cross-border fire risk zones; - Improved cooperation and Exchange; - Monitoring and modelling fire behavior
Fragiles Erbe/Kruche dziedzictwo UPWr Facebook	Develops automated systems for archaeological site documentation and analysis.	Potential for integrating historical environmental data into Climate_CRICES' adaptation planning.	<p>Focus: impacts of climate change on cultural monuments in Saxony and parts of Poland</p> <p>Key findings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing temperatures and fluctuating groundwater levels; - Impacts on archaeological sites and forest management; - Catalogue of recommendations for protecting monuments; - Future risk assessments and monument monitoring
TWIN-Waters	Develops digital tools for sustainable water resources management, integrating climate and land use impacts.	Contributes to Climate_CRICES' objectives by providing data-driven solutions for water-related climate risks.	<p>Focus: Develops digital tools for sustainable water resources management, integrating climate and land use impacts.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Smartening" and digitalizing the water system; - New sensor technologies; - Water quality modelling; - Citizen science and educational activities
CICADA4CE	Enhances climate adaptation in CE cities through ecosystem and community-based approaches, involving citizens in co-creating action plans.	Shared focus on community engagement and adaptation strategies for heat, drought, and flooding.	<p>Focus: adaptation planning using the ecosystem services approach;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong involvement of communities, including school pupils; - Pilot actions in Břeclav testing concrete adaptation measures
Polish Ministry of Climate and Environment			Mention of the recent ecological disaster (mass fish mortality); discussion of climate-related impacts on water systems; updating the river basin management plan - climate change must be integrated.
LIFE project - Liberec region (CZ, pending funding decision)	Work includes climate monitoring, evaluating adaptation measure effectiveness, and awareness-raising		Climate change focus in Liberecky region, activities related with data and monitoring, assessment of effectivity of measures, pilot actions implemented in Liberecky region, connected to activities how to increase the awareness (pupils as well), The project is currently awaiting a decision on support.

- 1) Johanna Kranz from Dresden University of Technology presented a project implemented under the Interreg Central Europe program: "Enabling cross-boundary assessment, communication and management of wildfire risks in Central Europe," acronym: Wildfire CE. The project addresses vegetation fires in Central Europe. Forecasts indicate that the number of days with high fire danger will increase annually from 10 to 20 days by 2080. Johanna Kranz presented the project's main objectives: e.g. improvement of maps (water sources, access roads), harmonization of fire danger levels in border areas, simulation of fire behavior, identification of risk areas, improvement of cross-border cooperation.
- 2) Next, Jan Macháč presented the Fragiles Erbe/Kruche dziedzictwo (Fragile Heritage) project on behalf of the absent presenter. The project is implemented under the Poland-Saxony Operational Program by Landesamt für Archäologie Sachsen and Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences. The Fragile Heritage project's objectives are e. g.: assessing the impact of climate change on archaeological monuments in the model region of Upper Lusatia on both the Saxon and Polish sides, establishment of a catalog of recommendations and measures for the protection of endangered monuments, development of guidelines for action plans for the adaptation of archaeological heritage to climate change. The project utilizes e. g. archaeological field research, digital field research, and climate data and forecasts.
- 3) The next presenter was Radostaw Stodolak, who introduced the Twin-Waters project (Digital Tools for Sustainable Water Resources Management: Integrating Impact), implemented jointly with Lund University and University of the West of England. Each partner addresses a separate case study. Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences focuses on the Wrocław city moat. The project aims to enhance the resilience of the city and ecosystem services against future climate challenges, particularly regarding downstream water quality issues like eutrophication, harmful algal blooms, and pathogenic contamination. The project employs innovative digitalization and new sensors. One of the activities involves finding a new sensor, which is validated in all case studies, created by the University of Bristol and tested in all three cases. It includes satellite services for water quality monitoring and modeling—one of the most important aspects of the project, encompassing hydrological modeling and water quality modeling.
- 4) Jan Macháč then presented the CICADA4CE project (Efficiency of the Climate Change Adaptation management by integration of ecosystem services and smart social approaches in Central European cities) on behalf of the absent Project Manager, Anna Starzewska-Sikorska. The project is implemented by partners from 6 countries. The project focuses on developing solutions with cities for climate change adaptation that should be implemented and differentiating strategies depending on different types of residents.
- 5) Next, Justyna Filipowicz from the Polish Ministry of Climate and Environment spoke. She informed participants that the Ministry is currently implementing many projects. One is related to climate change adaptation—they are working on a new national adaptation plan. There is a plan from 2013, which needs to be updated. The ministry wants to gather stakeholders' points of view: institutions, self-government institutions, but also others such as civil society and NGOs. The Ministry cooperates with the Institute of Environmental Protection, which conducts climate risk assessments. Water management is one of the biggest issues in climate adaptation, as is agriculture, which is also connected with water management. They plan to publish a new national adaptation plan by the end of 2027. Another project implemented by the Polish ministry focuses primarily on the eastern part of Poland. The east needs greater government support than the western part. This is related to legislative changes concerning more regional adaptation

plans. The legal provisions directly specify what adaptation plans for large cities should contain and what should be assessed. Local authorities can decide whether existing adaptation plans are sufficient or should be revised. Large cities are obligated to create adaptation plans, but it is also possible for smaller ones. They need more guidance.

- 6) Subsequently, Louis Courseau from the Polish Ministry of Climate and Environment shared his perspective. His work focuses on the Oder River. The ecological disaster on the Oder is a good example of climate change effects. The Ministry is focusing on developing indicators to prevent this type of disaster.
- 7) Magdalena Stanecka informed the participants about the reports that the Institute develops:
 - River Basin Management Plan for the International Odra River Basin District
 - Flood Risk Management Plan for the International Odra River Basin District, both of which address climate change-related issues.
- 8) Next, Jan Macháč briefly presented the Life Project, which is planned for implementation between 2027-2036. The project concerns climate change adaptation, and pilot actions will be conducted in the Liberec Region and will include, among other things, increasing awareness among pupils.

3.4 Interactive Deliberation: Exploring Synergies

The second part of the meeting included a workshop session. Participants were divided into 2 groups. Each group was provided with a whiteboard (fig. 2) and asked to reflect on the following issues:

1. What are the key challenges and data needs for effective:
 - a. HEAT AND DROUGHT adaptation
 - a. FLOOD adaptation and management
 - a. BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION AND RESTORATION
2. What forms of support do municipalities need for effective adaptation, and how can we strengthen them?
3. Where do you see the greatest opportunities for collaboration to enhance climate adaptation?
4. What are possible next steps?

After discussing the above-mentioned issues in groups, representatives from both groups presented the results to the plenary.

Fig. 2. One of the whiteboards used during the session

BREAKOUT SESSION RESULTS (Whiteboards outcomes)

1. Key Challenges - Climate Data Gaps and Limitations

General issues:

- Different data granularity across countries → difficult cross-border comparison
- Inconsistent calculation methods and modelling approaches
- Lack of data in small catchments and tributaries
- Sparse and uneven monitoring networks
- Legislative differences affecting data availability, frequent changes of officials and the lack of a continued strategy for cooperation
- Citizen preferences often conflict with technically informed adaptation needs
- Single-language portals, different navigation and data presentation

Heat & Drought:

- Data is often too coarse; inadequate urban-scale data (UHI)
- Heavy reliance on historical data rather than future projections

Flooding:

- No data in some small flood zones
- Missing harmonized datasets for flood risk

Biodiversity:

- Lack of indicators → difficult to monitor trends and success of measures
- Fragmented data sources

2. Supporting Municipal Adaptation - Needs and Barriers

Main barriers for municipalities:

- Very limited staff capacity; climate adaptation is not their main job
- Lack of expertise → uncertainty about what to implement
- Funding shortages ("money!")
- Fear of "poor outcomes" if measures fail

Municipal needs:

- Clear guidance and practical frameworks for implementation
- Good practice examples demonstrating successful adaptation efforts
- Tools to communicate benefits of nature-based solutions (NBS) to citizens
- More hands-on expert support

3. Opportunities for Cross-border Collaboration

- Sharing hands-on experience from pilot actions
- Stronger integration of ecological and technical experts
- Improving coordination between national and local levels
- Development of joint datasets and harmonized indicators
- Collaboration on monitoring and evaluation of adaptation measures
- Potential for a cross-border technical working group

4. Possible Next Steps

- Linking existing projects and organizing bilateral meetings
- Opening project outputs for upscaling and shared use
- Developing integrated cross-border platforms for climate and hydrology data
- Exploring joint questions such as:
 - Effectiveness of measures after 6 months
 - Monitoring contaminants (pesticides, antibiotics) in water
- Follow-up:
 - Johanna: will discuss continuity with her project leadership and keep contact with the leader of Wildfire project
 - Further cooperation

3.5 Wrap-Up and Next Steps

The discussion highlighted several potential next steps for enhancing cross-border collaboration. Participants emphasized the importance of linking existing projects and organizing bilateral meetings to foster closer cooperation. Opening project outputs for upscaling and shared use was seen as a key opportunity, alongside developing integrated cross-border platforms for climate and hydrology data. Joint exploration of specific questions, such as the effectiveness of measures after six months and the monitoring of contaminants like pesticides and antibiotics in water, was also proposed. As a follow-up, Johanna will discuss project continuity with her leadership team and maintain contact with the leader of the Wildfire project.

Overall, there is strong willingness to collaborate across borders, although practical barriers remain, particularly in terms of data harmonization. Municipalities need capacity building, technical expertise, and clearer guidance to translate plans into concrete adaptation actions. The region faces shared risks—including heat, drought, and flooding—that call for integrated monitoring and joint data frameworks. Moving forward, efforts should focus on unifying data formats, indicators, and methodologies, strengthening local capacities, and launching joint monitoring initiatives.

At the end of the meeting Climate CRICES team presented plans for the future activities, and invited participants to get involved in the upcoming Pilot Actions (presentation can be found [here](#))

4. Summary of Stakeholder Inputs

4.1 Prioritised Climate Risks

According to voting results, most participants identified heat and drought were identified as the top shared concern.

4.2 Identified Barriers

Participants identified the following challenges and data gaps, among others:

HEAT AND DROUGHT

- Cross-border differences in declarations from local authorities,
- Missing high-resolution data and in-situ validation of fuel types and moisture,
- In the context of rivers:
 - data gaps, e.g., concerning small catchments,
 - lack of methodology for calculating low flow,
 - different results arising from the application of different methodologies,
 - reliance on historical data instead of forecasts,
 - lack of homogeneous long-term historical data.

FLOOD ADAPTATION AND MANAGEMENT

- Legal regulations,
- Methods designed for large rivers often do not apply to small waterways,
- Sparse and uneven monitoring,
- Knowledge and information exists, there is a need for implementation and planning,
- Different measures (conflicting) on both sides of the river,
- Political changes in public institutions and a lack of continuity.

BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION AND RESTORATION

- Calculation methods differ,
- We are using historical data instead of projections,
- Different water quality monitoring levels and how this affects biodiversity in different countries in transboundary settings,
- Not enough scientific data and information on biodiversity loss,
- Missing information/data,
- Data is fragmented, difficult to access and there are no region-wide databases,
- Data mostly connected only with single case studies,
- Missing monitoring which will be repeated after several years.

4.3 Identified Needs

Participants identified the following needs to support municipal adaptation, among others:

- Clear guidance and practical frameworks for implementation
- Good practice examples demonstrating successful adaptation
- Providing a framework and hands-on support, including the feedback of authorities when creating action plans and platforms,
- Translating meteorological data into effects that require adaptation measures, providing capacities (money, people) -> a task for the government, involving citizens: not only through formal consultations but also via other communication channels, including the wishes of authorities when creating action plans or platforms.

4.4 Opportunities for Cooperation

Participants identified the following **opportunities for collaboration** to enhance climate adaptation, among others:

- Ecological NGOs as a bridge between national and local levels,
- field trips to local governments to demonstrate how they can adapt their cities.

Proposals for **next steps to collaborate across projects and institutions**, include:

- Opening up projects (upscaling)
- Outputs not only as pilots but on a larger scale
- Assessment of the effects of projects within approximately 6 months' time.

4.5 Overall Conclusions

- There is a strong willingness for **cross-border collaboration**, yet practical barriers persist, especially regarding **data harmonization**
- Municipalities require **capacity building, expertise, and clearer guidance** to move from plans to concrete adaptation actions
- The region shares common risks: heat, drought, flooding, that require integrated monitoring and joint data frameworks
- Next steps should focus on:
 - o Unifying data formats, indicators, and methodologies
 - o Strengthening local capacities
 - o Joint monitoring initiatives
 - o Creating stable communication channels between institutions

5. Implications for Pilot Action Design

5.1 Priority Themes for Pilot Actions

- Heat and drought -> Flooding -> Biodiversity loss
 - It must be noted, that this conclusion concerns only this workshop

5.2 Processes that need testing

- Challenges concerning data: units, granularity, methods of calculation.
- Filling data gaps in small catchments
- Improving cross-border monitoring
- Development of harmonised datasets
- Clear, practical guidance for municipalities

5.3 Limitations to consider

- In the case of biodiversity loss, focus on indicators that are easily accessible to all countries and can be operative (consultations with relevant institutions needed).
- Because municipalities struggle with limited resources, Pilot Actions must include clear, easy-to-apply steps that show how to move from data to planning decisions. Templates, short procedures, and simple guidance are essential.
- Pilot Actions must verify whether the processes proposed in the Climate_CRICES Strategy, especially those for integrating data into adaptation plans are realistic and workable within the different institutional settings of Poland, Czechia, and Germany.

5.4 Proposed PA ideas (optional)

- Addressing gaps in flood data and harmonizing flood-risk datasets
- Provide practical frameworks and examples (dashboard) for municipal adaptation

5.5 Recommendations (lesson learned)

- Focus on unifying data formats, indicators, and methodologies
- Build stable communication channels between institutions

6. Annexes

- List of participants
- List of other identified projects that have synergies with CLimate_CRICES
- Screenshots/whiteboards

List of participants:

1. Tamara Avellán,
2. Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz
3. Jan Macháč,
4. Štěpánka Truhlářová,
5. Lenka Zaňková
6. Eric Neuber,
7. Marco Neubert
8. Radosław Stodolak
9. Paula Krupková
10. Johanna Kranz
11. Magdalena Stanecka
12. Justyna Filipowicz
13. Louis Courseau
14. Michaela Dziadková
15. Anna Jastrzębska
16. Katarzyna Szeremeta

List of other identified projects that have synergies with CLimate_CRICES:

Project (link)	Description	Synergies with Climate_CRICES
BorderLabs CE	Improves cross-border governance and cooperation in Central Europe, focusing on sustainable development and participatory approaches.	Supports Climate_CRICES' transnational objectives, fostering collaboration across borders.
CrossWater	Addresses water-related climate risks through cross-border cooperation and innovative solutions.	Directly complements Climate_CRICES' focus on water-related climate adaptation.
ProAdapt	Focuses on mobilizing the private sector for climate resilience through tools and business models for MSMEs.	Aligns with Climate_CRICES by integrating economic resilience into adaptation strategies.
UPSURGE	Develops the EU Regenerative Urban Lighthouse, promoting nature-based solutions (NBS) to enhance urban resilience against climate change.	Aligns with Climate_CRICES' goals by integrating NBS for heat, drought, and biodiversity challenges.
KLIMADA 3.0	"Klimada 3.0 - Access to knowledge and data on climate change" aims to expand knowledge and improve access to climate data to support effective adaptation.	It will develop a science-based platform and open information sources enabling informed decisions on climate adaptation at all levels.
Urbio Bauhaus	Combats urban biodiversity decline by integrating New European Bauhaus principles into urban planning.	Enhances biodiversity aspects of Climate_CRICES, offering innovative urban solutions.

Meeting screenshot:

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. At the top, the meeting title is 'Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz's st...'. Below the title bar, there are five video thumbnails of participants: Lenka Zankova, Tamara Avellan, Štěpánka Truhlářová, Marco Neubert, and Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz. The main content area displays a dashboard titled 'Open Data Veneto' with the subtitle 'Increasing Climate Change Resilience in Central Europe'. The dashboard includes a 'Project summary' section with text about climate projections and data availability. To the right of the dashboard is a 'Participants (16)' list with names and initials, such as Lenka Zankova, Jan Machac, and Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz. A green circle with the number '12' is overlaid on the bottom right of the dashboard area. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the search bar with 'Hledat', several application icons, and the system tray with the time '9:32' and date '20.11.2025'.

Dashboard: First release

Landing Page

The official landing page for the dashboard has been released and it is publicly available at

https://dati.veneto.it/content/increasing_climate_change_resilience_central_europe#

Whiteboard group 1:

Introduction 0

Cross- and trans-border workshop on the current knowledge of climate data and information in support of climate change adaptation strategies in the Neisse Catchment

we'll go through the whiteboard together, step by step

if you have any difficulties using the board - please unmute and let us know

use hand-tool (bottom right corner) to navigate the board

use arrow-tool (top left side) to select

Step 1

1 Common challenges and data gaps

Unavailability of data in the whole cross-border area with comparable granularity and content

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **HEAT AND DROUGHT** adaptation?

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **FLOOD** adaptation and management?

problem with national languages--> hard to find the data

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION AND RESTORATION** ?

Conflict of interests with city authorities and history heritage consumer

Cross-border differences in interpretations from local authorities

Missing high-resolution data and in-situ validation of fuel types and moisture

Heat & Drought

Knowledge and information is existing, there is a need for implementation in planning

Different presentation and indicators on the flood hazard maps

Different measures implementing on the both sides of the river

Political changes in public institutions and a lack of the continuity

Flooding

Missing information/data

Data is fragmented, difficult to access and there are no region-wide databases

Calendar mostly connected only with precipitation, which will be repeated after winter or year

1 or of talking, but very little data

Kurznotiz

Step 2

2 Supporting municipal adaptation

showing best practice examples

providing a framework and hands-on support

Include wishes of authorities when creating action plans or platforms

What forms of support do municipalities need for effective adaptation, and how can we strengthen them?

capacities should be provided (training, courses, tasks for the government)

Translation of meteorological data into effects that need an adaptation measures

Transference of climate not only as formal consultations, but also as continuous communication channels

Notes

Step 3

3 Opportunities for collaboration

interlink between projects

Shared datasets

Harmonized indicators

publish the table with indicators used

Where do you see the greatest opportunities for collaboration to enhance climate adaptation?

initial step: publishing of the table with all projects relevant to Neisse catchment

continuous mutual updating regarding the developments in the ongoing projects

Notes

Step 4

Possible next steps

to link the projects

bilateral specific meetings

integrating platforms

Common space for sharing experiences (hosted by inter-regional institutions)

Notes

Whiteboard group 2:

Introduction 1

Cross- and trans-border workshop on the current knowledge of climate data and information in support of climate change adaptation strategies in the Neisse Catchment

We'll go through the whiteboard together, step by step

If you have any difficulties using the board - please unmute and let us know

use hand-tool (bottom right corner) to navigate the board

use arrow-tool (top left side) to select

Step 1

1 Common challenges and data gaps

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **HEAT AND DROUGHT** adaptation?

Prognose / trend on hydroclimatic data ex: min Q / mean Q in 20 years

hydro-meteorological data current land use data

granularity issues -- often too coarse

data harmonization

Heat & Drought

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **FLOOD** adaptation and management?

projections uncertainties

communication difficulties?

many different stakeholders with controversial mindset

no data in a small catchments (flow value, flood zones)

Relationship of flood directives with WFD and how to think those together

legal regulations

Methods designed for large rivers often do not apply to small waterways

sparse and uneven monitoring

Flooding

What are the key challenges and data needs for effective **BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION AND RESTORATION**?

No enough scientific data and information on biodiversity loss and relation to CC and their effective adaptation measures

Different water quality monitoring levels and of how they affect biodiversity in different countries in contemporary settings

calculation methods differ

we using historical instead of projections

citizens preferences

Kurzmetz

hydro-meteorological conditions and the observed states that allow for ecological disasters to happen

Step 2

2 Supporting municipal adaptation

What forms of support do municipalities need for effective adaptation, and how can we strengthen them?

show citizens benefits of NBS

UHI

show good practice - how can we adapt cities

money!

missing expertise

How to implement

poor outcome

Notes

Step 3

3 Opportunities for collaboration

Where do you see the greatest opportunities for collaboration to enhance climate adaptation?

ecological NGO as bridge between national and local

hands-on experience

national level vs local level roles

bigger focus on technical site?

Notes

Step 4

Possible next steps

cooperation

open the projects (upscaling)

effect of projects in ca. 5 month time

outputs not only for pilots but in bigger extent

cooperate together on the topic of antibiotics in water?

Notes